

TALLINN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY
SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING
Department of Materials and Environmental Technology

**EVALUATING THE ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY OF
NANOCOMPOSITE SORBENT MATERIALS FOR
PHOSPHORUS RECOVERY FROM WASTEWATER
USING BACTERIA *VIBRIO FISCHERI***

**REOVEEST FOSFORIT SORBEERIVATE
NANOKOMPOSIITMATERJALIDE KESKKONNAOHUTUSE
MÄÄRAMINE KASUTADES TESTBAKTEREID *VIBRIO
FISCHERI***

MASTER THESIS

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Tallinn, 2022

(On the reverse side of title page)

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Thesis topic:

(In English) *EVALUATING THE ENVIRONMENTAL SAFETY OF NANOCOMPOSITE SORBENT MATERIALS FOR PHOSPHORUS RECOVERY FROM WASTEWATER USING BACTERIA VIBRIO FISCHERI*

(In Estonian) REOVEEST FOSFORIT SORBEERIVATE NANOKOMPOSIITMATERJALIDE KESKKONNAOHUTUSE MÄÄRAMINE KASUTADES TESTBAKTEREID *VIBRIO FISCHERI*

Thesis main objectives:

1. To evaluate the physicochemical characteristics of 10 engineered nanocomposite materials for phosphorus adsorption using three different methods:
 - Settling tests to assess the stability of the nanocomposite suspensions,
 - Total reflection X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (TXRF) to analyse the dissolved metal concentration in the filtrates of the particle suspensions,
 - Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) to determine the hydrodynamic size and the surface charge of the nanocomposite particles.
2. To investigate the 10 nanocomposite materials with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* toxicity screening test using two different endpoints:
 - Inhibition of bacterial bioluminescence - modified Flash assay and
 - Ability to form visible colonies on agar plate after the exposure to the nanocomposites – Spot assay.
3. To identify possible candidates of nanocomposite materials to be used in future studies/applications for phosphorus recovery from wastewater.

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PREFACE

The subject for the thesis was proposed by researcher and the main supervisor Asya Ivanova Drenkova-Tuhtan. Current work is contributing to the project “NanoPhosTox” (Grant agreement ID: 867457) funded by the European Commission within the MSCA-IF-EF-ST action of the Horizon 2020 program H2020-EU.4 [1]. The practical work was conducted at National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics (NICPB) in the Laboratory of Environmental Toxicology (head of laboratory Dr. Anne Kahru). Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan and Mariliis Sihtmäe consulted, supported and guided the author during the work.

The aim of this thesis was to perform environmental safety assessment of the selected 10 custom nanocomposite (NC) sorbent materials for phosphorus recovery from wastewater towards *Vibrio fischeri*. The work was divided into three main parts:

1. Characterization of the physicochemical properties of the nanocomposite materials using dynamic light scattering (DLS) method, settling tests and total reflection X-ray fluorescence (TXRF) spectroscopy;
2. Conducting a high-throughput toxicity screening with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* using two endpoints: inhibition of bacterial bioluminescence (modified Flash assay; exposure time 30 min) and ability to yield visible colonies on agar plate after the exposure to the nanocomposites (Spot assay; exposure time 2 and 24 h);
3. Identifying possible candidates of nanocomposite materials for future applications in phosphorus recovery from wastewater.

The physicochemical characterization of the nanocomposite materials revealed fast settling properties and large hydrodynamic particle size (in lower μm -range) for most of the samples, which was in contradiction with the initial hypothesis that the size distribution of the materials is only in the nano-range. This reflected on the conclusions regarding the materials interactions with the test organism and the expected toxicity mechanisms and required recommending a different particle-size characterization method, discussed thoroughly in the thesis.

According to the first screening for possible toxicity of selected materials, the results were in line with the hypothesis and majority of evaluated nanocomposite materials

were not classified as toxic¹ (30 min EC₅₀ > 37 mg / L) to the selected test organism bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*.

I would like to thank my supervisor Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan and co-supervisor Mariliis Sihtmäe for their guidance, time and patience during the experimental part and writing of the thesis. Additionally, I am grateful to all the NICPB personnel, especially Heiki Vija, for their kindness and support during the work in the Laboratory of Environmental Toxicology. Special thank you to the head of the laboratory, Dr. Anne Kahru, for giving me the opportunity to undertake this research.

Key words: bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, ecotoxicology, acute toxicity, nanocomposite sorbent materials, master thesis.

¹ Hazard classification criteria [2] of the chemicals used in ecotoxicology on the basis of EC₅₀ values: extremely toxic if EC₅₀ ≤ 0.1 mg / L; very toxic if 0.1 < EC₅₀ ≤ 1 mg / L; toxic if 1 < EC₅₀ ≤ 10 mg / L; harmful if 10 < EC₅₀ ≤ 100 mg / L; not classified if EC₅₀ > 100 mg / L.

List of abbreviations and symbols

BH - *Beneckea harvey*

CRM – Critical Raw Materials

Dh – Hydrodynamic diameter

DI – Deionised water

DLS – Dynamic Light Scattering

EC₅₀ – the median effective concentration, which in the context of this study refers to the concentration of a chemical reducing the bacterial bioluminescence by 50 % after contact time of 30 min

ECHA – European Chemicals Agency

ELS – Electrophoretic Light Scattering

EU – European Union

HD – Hydrodynamic diameter

ISO – International Organization for Standardization

LC₅₀ – the median lethal concentration of the chemical that induces a designated effect in 50 % of the test organisms after a specified exposure time

MBC – Minimum bactericidal concentration

MP – Magnetic particle

NC – Nanocomposite

NICPB – National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics

P – Phosphorus

PDI – Polydispersity Index

QSAR – Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship

RLU – Relative Light Units

SD – Standard Deviation

TXRF – Total Reflection X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy

INTRODUCTION

Phosphorus deficiency is a globally growing concern. Phosphorus is one of the main nutrients for all living beings and therefore a vital fertilizer for the growth of crops and global food security. One way to obtain phosphorus is through mining phosphate rock, which is a geographically unevenly distributed, non-renewable and scarce resource. This in turn is a serious threat to regions with limited or no phosphate rock reserves, which, for geopolitical and economic reasons, are heavily dependent on imports of phosphate rock. Furthermore, mining a non-renewable resource causes a severe negative impact on the environment. Nevertheless, it is possible to recover phosphorus which is already in our ecosystem and close the resource loop. Significant quantities of phosphorus can be found in municipal wastewater. Recovering phosphorus from the wastewater may not only offset the fertilizer deficiency problem but would also contribute to the reduction of possible eutrophication issues in the receiving water bodies. Regulatory discharge limit values are set for maximum allowable phosphorus concentration in wastewater effluents and therefore it is necessary to remove the phosphorus from wastewater beforehand. Phosphorus recovery is contributing also to the circular economy model and therefore is more sustainable than the conventional phosphate rock mining.

According to the previous research, engineered nanocomposite particles are found to be highly efficient for phosphorus recovery from wastewaters. This thesis work is part of the "NanoPhosTox" [1] project whose main goal is to evaluate the toxicity of the phosphorus adsorbing engineered nanocomposite particles to the aquatic environment. It is critical to test the nanocomposite materials for toxicity due to the risk of possible particle discharge or leaching of the particle precursors after the wastewater treatment process in the effluent of the treatment plant.

Advantage of using the proposed nanocomposite materials is the highly efficient recovery of phosphorus from wastewater based on reversible sorption, and the ability to reuse the nanocomposite particles numerous times after their regeneration [3]. These benefits are achieved by coating magnetic particles with nanostructured adsorbent materials [4] [5] and using permanent magnets to collect particles from the wastewater. Change in pH allows desorption of phosphorus from the composite particles which after regeneration are ready for the next application.

The author of this thesis chose the topic due to the above-mentioned concerns and the desire to contribute to improving novel technologies to support the circular economy

and sustainable use of resources. Furthermore, knowing that the current work contributes to the national and international goals from Estonia, the European Union and United Nations on the sustainable use of resources and promotion of circular economy, as well as novel technologies for more sustainable resource use, was an important drive towards supporting the research in this area. Finally, personal interest in the toxicity screening procedures and the precision in the field were an additional motivation to choose this Master's thesis topic.

The main problem that the current thesis is addressing is the lack of consistent toxicity data that could be used for the environmental safety assessment on novel nanocomposite phosphorus adsorption materials.

The main objective of this thesis is to evaluate the environmental safety of ten nanocomposite sorbent materials for phosphorus recovery from wastewater to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. Nanocomposites used in the current research were synthesised by the main supervisor Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan as a part of the "NanoPhosTox" project. More specifically, the current work fulfils three main tasks within the analysis of the selected nanocomposite materials:

1. Physicochemical characterization (dynamic light scattering method, settling test and reflection X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy);
2. Toxicity screening with *V. fischeri* using kinetic bioluminescence inhibition (modified Flash assay; exposure time 30 min) and viability (Spot assay; exposure time 2 h and 24 h) test;
3. Identification of possible candidates of nanocomposite materials to be used for phosphorus adsorption.

The thesis consists of three main sections:

1. Literature review – gives an overview on the importance of phosphorus as a non-replaceable nutrient, technologies for its recovery, and bacteria as the unicellular organisms for the cost-effective *in vitro* toxicity screening;
2. Materials and methodology – introduce the 10 nanocomposite materials developed for phosphate adsorption from wastewater and describes the methodologies used for their characterization and safety assessment (Free settling test, TXRF, DLS, modified Flash assay, Spot assay);
3. Results and discussion – present the findings of the current thesis in a table and graphical format, discusses assumptions and interprets the generated results, draws conclusions and makes further suggestions for the future research.

Appendices 1 to 3 are containing modified Flash assay test inhibition percentages with standard deviation for each composite, their filtrates and precursor salts at every tested concentration.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review gives an overview of the following three main topics: phosphorus, phosphorus recycling from wastewater, and bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* as a model organism for toxicity screening. The first section discusses the role of phosphorus in the life cycle, the areas where it is found, either naturally or due to anthropogenic activities, and its scarcity within the European Union. The second section covers various phosphorus recovery technologies, specifically the adsorption-based technology using nanostructured composite materials. The third section gives an overview of why bacteria are used for toxicity screening and provides an in-depth discussion on testing with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*.

1.1 Phosphorus and its importance

Phosphorus (P) is on one hand an environmental pollutant causing eutrophication in water bodies, but on the other hand, it is an essential nutrient for agriculture and therefore an important element for the global food security. Phosphorus has fundamental biological functions and is part of the structure of DNA, RNA, ATP, ADP, bones, cell membranes, etc. It is present in many organic compounds and is vital for the development and growth of all living organisms. Moreover, it is an essential chemical element for many important industrial products such as high-functional plastics, electronics, electric vehicles and pharmaceuticals. [6]

Phosphorus is also one of the key elements in the farming industry and a vital element for the plants [7]. Over 80 % of the mined phosphate rock is used as a fertilizer [6]. Phosphate rock reserves are scarce and found globally only in very few geographical locations. Currently, global research on phosphate resources has indicated that 70 % of the world's total phosphate reserves are located in Morocco and Western Sahara; 5 % in China; 3 % in Syria, Algeria; 2 % in Russia, South Africa, United States, Egypt and Jordan. In other countries phosphate reserves are 1 % or less. [8] [6] Due to the fact that P is a non-renewable resource with very limited global distribution and it is one of the key elements for plants, it creates a sustainability concern within the food industry. Its resources are becoming scarce and more expensive. [7]

Within the European Union (EU) a reliable access to certain raw materials should be provided continuously. To address this issue and consider possible supply risks, a list of

critical raw materials (CRMs) was introduced by the European Commission (EC) in 2011. [9] Phosphate rock was added to the EU CRMs list in 2014 [10]. The list contains materials which are economically important and whose supply is under a risk. These materials are part of the strong industrial base for the EU economy and are used in modern technologies and goods production. The list includes materials with high importance and high risk of supply chain disruption. The main goals of creating such a list are:

- to strengthen the competitiveness of the European economy;
- stimulate the production of CRMs;
- encourage efficient use and recycling of CRMs;
- increase awareness of potential raw material supply risks;
- and encourage more efficient raw materials trading. [9]

Furthermore, during the United Nations Rio Convention in 1992 it was agreed upon the principles of intergenerational justice which is a basic regulative concept. Its essence is to reduce opportunity costs for future generations and provide long-term access to high-grade deposits. Therefore, the disrupted phosphorus cycle must be closed again. Moreover, *cradle-to-cradle* technologies are rising in terms of competitiveness within economic development due to the increasing acknowledgement that closing loops and recycling are vital actions in the supply-demand chain. [6]

Considering the vital importance of phosphorus for our economy and for nature, as well as the risks associated with its accidental or deliberate release into the surrounding environment and the negative impact caused by mining this non-renewable resource, it is essential to investigate approaches that mitigate these issues. P needs to be removed where it is in excess, but at the same time it is a crucial element to assure global food security. In recent years many studies have researched possibilities and new methods to remove and recover phosphorus from wastewater. [4]

1.2 Phosphorus recovery technologies

There is a global concern that due to insufficient phosphorus removal from point sources of P-pollution such as wastewater treatment plants or violation of the P-discharge limit values for wastewater treatment before releasing the effluent into the receiving water

bodies, and especially due to phosphorus pollution from diffuse sources such as runoff from over-fertilized agricultural fields, many rivers and lakes have higher phosphorus content than the admissible immersion values for oligotrophic water bodies. In the United States over 90 % of the rivers in 12 out of 14 researched ecoregions exceeded the reference median values for phosphorus concentration in year 2008 and were at risk of eutrophication. The damage caused by high nutrient content in the aquatic systems resulted in total costs of around 2,2 billion dollars annually. [11] Therefore, it is vital to implement effective phosphorus removal technologies, especially at point sources such as municipal and industrial wastewater treatment plants. However, phosphorus is also a valuable nutrient and a scarce resource, so it is crucial to find ways to recover the phosphorus removed in wastewater treatment plants, which act like a sink for this valuable nutrient.

There are three main points where phosphorus can be recovered during the wastewater treatment process. These include phosphorus recovery from:

1. The wastewater liquid phase;
2. The sewage sludge;
3. The ash of the incinerated sewage sludge. [12]

According to the research conducted by Cornel and Schaum in 2009, phosphorus recovery from the wastewater liquid phase can reach 40 - 50 % efficiency and from the sludge ash up to 90 % recovery efficiency from the inflow P. Furthermore, at that time phosphorus recovery costs exceeded costs of mineral fertilizers many times. [12] Low efficiency in phosphorus recovery from wastewater indicates that technologies used were not very cost-effective, therefore it is vital to conduct further research in the area to increase the recovery efficiency with new technologies.

Some phosphorus recovery technologies that were found in the literature include:

- Alkaline leaching for phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge ash in the form of calcium hydroxyapatite. This technology has a full-scale plant in Japan with P recovery rate of 30 - 40 %;
- Thermochemical process at 1300 °C temperature to convert sewage sludge into slag. This technology is used in a full-scale plant in Japan with a P recovery rate of 90 %;

- Chemical precipitation with addition of magnesium ions to the anaerobically digested sludge to recover struvite crystals. This technology has a full-scale plant in Japan with P recovery rate of 40 – 90 %;
- CO₂ to recover phosphorus from wet sewage sludge. There is a pilot plant implemented in Germany.
- Reactive inorganic adsorbents (e.g. coal combustion fly ash) to recover phosphorus from wastewater. [6]

These technologies are also following the circular economy principles which are greatly reducing the negative environmental impact caused by mining. It is important to continue research for efficient phosphorus recovery technologies. Within the comparative study on 63 different inorganic and organic P adsorbents, it was found that different engineered nanocomposite materials like metal oxides and hydroxides have high phosphorus adsorption and desorption rate [13].

According to the definition of the European Commission, a nanomaterial is: "A natural, incidental or manufactured material containing particles, in an unbound state or as an aggregate or as an agglomerate and where, for 50 % or more of the particles in the number size distribution, one or more external dimensions are in the size range 1 nm - 100 nm. In specific cases and where warranted by concerns for the environment, health, safety or competitiveness the number size distribution threshold of 50 % may be replaced by a threshold between 1 and 50 % [14]."

The following definitions are given by the European Commission Scientific Committee:

- Nanomaterial – "Material with one or more external dimensions, or an internal structure, at nanoscale and which could exhibit novel characteristics compared to the same material at a larger scale. [15]" and
- Nanoscale – "having one or more dimensions of the order of 100 nm or less. [16]"

Nanocomposites materials are engineered materials, in which the size structure of the individual particles is in the nanoscale, but the composite as a whole may form agglomerates of the various compounds in it and result in microscale formations. [1]

In literature some nanotechnologies for phosphorus recovery, mostly adsorption-based, were studied. For example, Xia et al. reported that nanoscale magnesium oxide (MgO) has excellent phosphorus adsorption properties, although its adsorption capacity was not fully utilized and they proposed annealing to recover its adsorption capacity. With

this method P can be accumulated to high concentrations that are even surpassing its theoretical adsorption equilibrium limit. [17] Furthermore, hydrated ferric oxide (Fe_2O_3) nanocomposite system has been studied for phosphorus recovery in the form of struvite crystals. The P recovery rate was around 97 % and different molar ratios of the nanocomposite system were researched. It was stated that the addition of Ca^{2+} could also contribute to P recovery. This method was used in liquid bioeffluent. [18] Another method researched the P recovery from aqueous solution using biochar nanocomposites where biochar was functionalized with calcined dolomite. Biochar was synthesized via pyrolysis of winery derivatives (vinasse), which had a large adsorption surface area, and different weight ratios between biochar and dolomite were researched. [19]

Furthermore, metal oxide and hydroxide-based nanoparticles were reported as efficient adsorbents for phosphorus recovery. Complex synthesis strategy was performed for the fabrication of FeOOH /anion exchanger nanocomposites. These showed P adsorption rates close to 51 % under optimal conditions. It was concluded that three valent iron was the dominant active species to be included in the composition of that material. [20]

In recent years many technologies and materials were discovered which have the ability to remove and recycle phosphorus from wastewater. ZnFeZr-oxide/hydroxide-based multicomponent nanostructured material has shown very promising results for phosphate adsorption. Each component of the ZnFeZr-based nanostructured material was carefully selected during years of research to achieve highest adsorption efficiency. Different compositions and molar ratios were examined during the research to find the metals combination and nanocomposite material with the best phosphate adsorption characteristics. It was found that a combination of different two-, three- and four-valent metals as oxides/hydroxides have synergic properties which enhance the phosphate adsorption and desorption capacity of the material. [4]

These novel nanocomposite materials have shown extremely efficient phosphate adsorption results but the lack of data on their environmental safety outlines the demand for filling the existing research gaps. In the Web of Science database the following result were found including the terms:

1. "nanocomposite" and "phosphorus recovery": 8 articles were found;
2. "nanomaterial" and "phosphorus recovery": 3 articles were found;
3. "nano*" and "phosphorus recovery": 146 articles were found.

Separate addition of the terms "tox*", "safety", "vibrio fischeri", "bacteria" gave no results. Combined search with "nano*" and "phosphorus recovery" and "tox*" gave 6

results but none of these were relevant to the environmental safety assessment of nanocomposite materials used for P recovery from wastewater. Therefore, it is important to evaluate the possible ecotoxicity of the proposed nanocomposite materials.

The toxicity of nanocomposite materials is not a widely analysed area. The information on the toxicity screening of NPs is currently sparse. [21]

1.3 Bacteria for the toxicity testing

Toxicological bioassays are essential to monitor, evaluate, and predict the environmental hazards of chemicals to organisms and ecosystems. The ecotoxicological effects of chemicals (including nanocomposites) can be evaluated using different bioassays on environmentally relevant test species such as algae, crustaceans, fish, protozoa, earthworms, bacteria, and fungi. [22]

A search in the Web of Science made on 15th of May 2022 (see Table 1.1) showed that of algae, crustaceans, fish, protozoa, earthworms, bacteria and fungi, the most often used organisms for toxicity studies of nanocomposites were bacteria (756 publications published), and the toxicity data for protozoa and earthworms were both found only in 5 published articles out of 1010 publications.

Table 1.1 Share of scientific information on the ecotoxicity of nanocomposites for different environmentally relevant organism groups. Data were retrieved from the Web of Science on 15th of May 2022, using the search terms "nanocomposite*" AND "toxic*" AND "organism (e.g. algae; crustaceans; fish; protozoa; earthworms; bacteria; fungi)". The total number of publications was 1449.

Organism	Number of publications
bacteria	756
fungi	93
fish	76
algae	65
crustaceans	10
protozoa	5
earthworms	5

In the current thesis the focus was set to the toxicity testing with bacteria. Bacteria are relevant and favourable alternatives to higher organisms in toxicity testing as they are the simplest systems for (eco)toxicological studies on the whole-cell level. Bacteria are easy and cheap to handle and grow in laboratory conditions (e.g. short generation time; small test volumes and high numbers - $>10^6$ organisms per mL; possibility to store in freeze-dried condition; no advanced training of staff or ethical issues related). Due to the small size of bacteria the advantages of bacterial assays also include for example their high surface area to volume ratio and high statistical significance since the observed response is produced by a large number of cells. [22]

Moreover, for chemicals with a toxic action common for different types of organisms, such as interference with cellular membranes, bacteria are the most suitable test system for rapid screening of toxic potency [22].

Bacteria are omnipresent organisms, they are found everywhere in the surrounding environment (air, water and soil). They represent an important link in the food web as decomposers. The luminescent bacteria – *Vibrio fischeri* – and its bioluminescence inhibition assay has been widely applied in ecotoxicity testing and is applicable for an extensive variety of chemical substances as well as environmental and industrial samples. [23]

Vibrio fischeri (also known as *Photobacterium phosphoreum* and *Aliivibrio fischeri* [24]) is a gram-negative rod-shaped marine photobacterium [25], which inhabits in the light organs of monacentrid fish and certain squids [26].

Vibrio fischeri test system has been used for more than 40 years for rapid assessment of the ecotoxicity of aquatic samples [27], [25]. Several comparisons have been made between *V. fischeri* test (Microtox™) and other standardized bioassays. As a result good correlation with other aquatic organisms (e.g. algae, protozoa, crustaceans and fish) as well as animal, human cell lines, rodents, dog and humans has been shown (the correlation coefficients, R^2 , ranged between 0,20 - 0,79) [28], [29]. In addition, *V. fischeri* data are remarkably often used for the development of quantitative structure-activity relationships (QSARs) [30], [2]. QSAR models are empirical statistical models which are used in the biological and chemical engineering. These models are used to assess the biological activity quantitatively for example by estimating concentration of a chemical required to give a certain biological response. [31]

In *V. fischeri*, special lux genes are encoding the core enzymes (e.g. FMN-reductase and luciferase) responsible for their bioluminescence. In 1953, it was discovered by Strehler that nicotinate adenine dinucleotide in reduced form (NADH) activates the luminescence within the extracts of light emitting bacteria. Soon after that, important discovery was made that the luminescence reaction requires additionally to the luciferase and molecular oxygen, also riboflavin 5' – monophosphate in reduced form (FMNH₂) and a long-chain saturated aliphatic aldehyde (fatty aldehyde). During the luminescence reaction aldehyde is consumed and the total amount of light emitted is directly dependent on the aldehyde used. Therefore, the aldehyde is studied to be a luciferin - an organic substance that produces light when enzyme luciferase oxidises it. [32]

The bioluminescence of *V. fischeri* is a result of a complex chain of biochemical reactions. The most important reaction (1.1) for the luminescence process was documented by Cormier and Totter in 1957 and Hastings and Gibson in 1963 and represents the process of emitting light as follows:

where *FMNH₂* – riboflavin 5' – monophosphate in reduced form,

FMN – riboflavin 5' – monophosphate,

RCHO – fatty aldehyde,

RCOOH – fatty acid,

O₂ – oxygen molecule,

H₂O – water molecule. [32]

Light production is a measure of the overall “well-being” of the bacteria and bioluminescence is directly proportional to the metabolic status of the cell. *V. fischeri* is known to have a detectable peak wavelength of 475 nm and is therefore visible in the dark with no external light source. Evolutionally, luciferase of the bacteria helped to scavenge oxygen industrially and this property also found use in the toxicity screening of chemicals. [26]

In the frame of this study *V. fischeri* kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test (i.e Flash assay) was used to evaluate the toxic potency of the selected nanocomposite materials. The kinetic format of the *V. fischeri* test is an ISO standardized acute toxicity test (ISO 21338, 2010, [33]) and it is a modification of the conventional photobacterial bioluminescence inhibition assay (ISO 11348, 2018, [34]). In both assays the decrease of bacterial luminescence upon exposure to chemicals is dose-related to their toxic effects and results mostly from the damage to the bacterial membranes [26], [33]. The kinetic method overcomes the problems arising from intense colour and turbidity, which are common problems for nanomaterial suspensions: in this kinetic assay each sample acts as a reference for itself [35]. There is no need for sedimentation or centrifugation of turbid samples, or for the correction of colour as described in ISO 11348. [34]

V. fischeri modified kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test is applicable to:

- a) sediment samples and water suspensions of sediments (fresh water, brackish, and seawater sediments);
- b) effluents (especially turbid and coloured);
- c) aqueous extracts (e.g. leachates, eluates, elutriates) of soil, solid waste, and other solid material (especially turbid and coloured). [34]

Considering that suspensions of nanomaterials are often turbid due to insolubility and/or aggregation of particles, the kinetic format of the *V. fischeri* test is also appropriate for screening the toxicity of nanomaterials and nanocomposite materials used in this study.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This chapter gives an overview of the novel engineered materials which will be a subject of environmental safety evaluation, as well as the methodologies (e.g. physicochemical characterization and toxicity screening test) used to conduct the safety assessment. This chapter is divided into five sections. In the first section ten nanocomposite materials are introduced and a brief overview is given of their synthesis process and their characteristics. Sections two to four are discussing methodologies used for the characterization of the suspensions of nanocomposite materials, and the last section presents the toxicity testing in two sub-sections.

2.1 Nanocomposite materials

The current thesis focuses on 10 nanocomposite materials and additionally composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on magnetic particles (MPs) is considered as 11th composite listed in the Table 2.1. These ten composites were synthesised and selected for further analysis at the National Institute of Chemical Physics and Biophysics, Tallinn in October and November 2020 by the main thesis supervisor Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan. Additional information on the detailed synthesis procedures of the nanocomposites and the deposition of the nanocomposite onto magnetic particles can be found in the publications [5], [36] and is briefly described below. As the current thesis is part of the NanoPhosTox project [1], these ten materials were already pre-selected to be researched further if they comply with the environmental “safe-by-design” criteria. These ten materials were selected out of numerous previously researched materials due to their high efficiency in phosphorus recovery as well as difference in their precursor’s composition (Table 2.2).

Each element of NCs was carefully selected and plays a key role in the structure of the NCs. Zn oxides and hydroxides are proven to be efficient pollutant adsorbers. Fe in all forms (hydroxides, oxides, magnetite etc.) is efficient for adsorption of ions, cations and other dissolved substances like arsenic, which has similar properties to phosphorus (negatively charged, multivalent). Zr was added to the structure of the NCs as a doping element which improves the phosphorus adsorption capacity of the NCs. Ca and Mg are added to form a structure (layers) for layered double hydroxide. [4]

Table 2.1 List of the engineered nanocomposite sorbent particles (synthesized as water suspensions) with their nominal molar ratios of the precursor metal salts and dry mass concentrations of the stock suspensions with their respective pH values.

Nr	Composite name	Nominal molar ratios of the precursor salts					Dry mass concentration and pH of the particle stock suspensions	
		Ca ²⁺ salt	Mg ²⁺ salt	Zn ²⁺ salt	Fe ³⁺ salt	Zr ⁴⁺ salt	[g / L]	pH
1	ZnFeZr 18:5:1			18	5	1	45,7	6,7
2	ZnFeZr 10:1:1			10	1	1	23,7	6,5
3	ZnFeZr 6:1:1			6	1	1	16,8	6,7
4	ZnFeZr 4:1:1			4	1	1	12,2	6,9
5	ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1			3,6	0,2	1	9,9	6,6
6	CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	3		3	1	1	10,5	6,5
7	MgZnFe 1:1:1		1	1	1		9,7	7,2
8	CaFeZr 6:1:1	6			1	1	5,5	7,9
9	MgFeZr 6:1:1		6		1	1	5,8	8,5
10	CaFe 2:1	2			1		4,6	8,4
11	ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on magnetic particles (MPs)			6	1	1	56,0	8,0

Table 2.1 shows the 10 tested composites and additionally the composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 deposited on magnetic particles. From the table it is possible to read the nominal (theoretical) molar ratios of the metal salts used as precursors for the synthesis of the nanocomposite sorbent particles, as well as the dry mass concentration (in g / L) of their initial stock suspensions and their pH values. Table 2.2 shows the 5 different precursor salts used for the synthesis of the nanocomposites with the pH values of their water suspensions at 2 g / L concentration. pH values were measured with Jenway 3310 pH-meter.

Table 2.2 List of precursor salts and their respective stock suspensions pH.

Precursor salt	Concentration [g / L]	pH
CaCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O	2	6,3
MgCl ₂ · 6H ₂ O	2	6,8
ZnCl ₂	2	6,4
FeCl ₃ · 6H ₂ O	2	1,9
ZrOCl ₂ · 8H ₂ O	2	1,8

Salts containing various two-, three- and four-valent metals, such as Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} and Zr^{4+} (see Table 2.2), were used as precursors for the co-precipitation synthesis of the nanocomposite adsorbent particles.

According to the synthesis procedure, the respective amounts of the precursor salts (Table 2.2) were taken and dissolved in deionised water (Millipore Milli-Q® Water Purification System). Then, sodium hydroxide (NaOH) was added drop-by-drop using a peristaltic pump. Afterwards the suspension was neutralized with hydrochloric acid (HCl) to pH 6 - 8,5 which is suitable to perform testing with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* according to the standard ISO 11348, 2018 [34]. Furthermore, the as-synthesized particle suspensions were washed with deionised water 3 times *via* centrifugation. For the final step, five to ten grams of nanocomposites were dispersed in deionised water and thus, the synthesis of the initial stock suspensions was completed (see Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1 Stock suspensions (in deionized water) of the as-synthesized engineered nanocomposite sorbent particles to be used in the *Vibrio fischeri* toxicity tests. Remark: The dry mass concentration of the stock suspensions is listed in Table 2.1.

The actual concentrations of the particle stock suspensions were determined by measuring the dry residue of each sample after drying at 105 °C. The standard drying procedure was performed by the main supervisor Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan following the standard DIN 38409. For this purpose, 100 mL of each well homogenized sample were dosed into crucibles and dried in a laboratory oven at 105 °C until constant mass. Each sample was measured twice and the average values are listed in Table 2.1 (standard deviation between the two measurements was within the +/- 5 % range for all samples). This work was out of scope of the current thesis and the results in Table 2.1 were directly provided by the supervisor.

The stock suspensions of all 11 composite materials were prepared in DI water (see Table 2.1), diluted to the target concentration of 2 g / L and homogenised using an ultrasonic probe (Branson Digital Sonifier®, USA) at 40 W for 2 min once before testing. As discussed later in Section 3.1, most of the composites were in the higher nano- or micro- range, due to the possible agglomeration effects in the particle suspensions.

In addition, filtrates of composite materials were prepared and analysed. For that, initially homogenized stocks were filtered through a 0,1 µm syringe filter. Precursor salt stocks were made by weighing previously calculated amounts of precursor salts and addition of deionised water to reach the target concentration of 2 g / L.

Nanocomposite initial stocks (see Figure 2.1) were stored in the dark at room temperature of approximately 22 °C. Diluted stocks, their filtrates and precursor stocks were always freshly prepared from initial stocks on the day of the experiment.

2.2 Free settling test

To assess the stability of the nanocomposite materials, a free settling test in DI water and 2 % NaCl solution (testing medium for *V. fischeri*) was conducted. For that, the following dilutions relevant for the toxicity tests were prepared from all ten nanocomposite materials: 0,1; 1; 10; 100; 500 and 1000 [mg / L].

To determine the settling ability of the particle samples, 1 mL of suspension was pipetted into 1,5 mL cuvettes and images were taken at different time intervals: 0 min; 30 min; 4 h; 24 h. These time points were chosen according to the length of bacterial tests (30 min bioluminescence inhibition test, 2 h and 24 h viability test).

2.3 Total Reflection X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy (TXRF)

The concentration of metals (dissolved fraction of the composite materials) in the filtrates was analysed by total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (TXRF) using the Picofox S2 device (Bruker AXS Microanalysis GmbH, Germany; detection limit 1 ppb). The molybdenum-targeted air-cooled X-ray tube generates X-rays, which are reduced to a narrow energy range by a multilayer monochromator. The TXRF methodology is capable of multielement analysis at ultra-trace concentrations. [37]

All metals used as precursors for the synthesis of the nanocomposite particles (Zn, Fe, Zr, Ca and Mg) could be analysed with the Picofox instrument.

Briefly, the suspensions of the composite materials were filtered through a 0,1 μm syringe filter (Sartorius Minisart), then the filtrates were mixed with the gallium standard solution in the volume ratio 1:1 and 5 μL of each sample mixture were pipetted onto quartz carrier discs. The discs were heated at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to evaporate the water from a small drop of sample, positioned exactly in the centre of the plate. To ensure this, the plates were pre-cleaned and treated with silicone oil. The concentration of metals was quantified with the Spectra software (AXS Microanalysis GmbH, Germany). Each individual measurement took 300 seconds and the total measurement time was about 2 hours.

During the filtration with 0,1 μm syringe filter only the dissolved fraction passes through the filter. Therefore, using TXRF methodology allows to map the dissolved metal concentrations for composites dispersed in deionised water.

2.4 Hydrodynamic size and surface charge

Hydrodynamic size and surface charge (ζ - potential) of studied composite materials in DI water was measured by the dynamic light scattering and electrophoretic light scattering method. For that, Zetasizer Nano ZS and Zetasizer software 6.32 (Zetasizer Nano-ZS, Malvern Instruments, UK) were used (maximum size range, diameter: 0,3 nm to 10 μm and size range for ζ - potential, diameter: 3,8 nm to 100 μm). Zetasizer is

equipped with a 4,0 mW 633 nm laser (Model ZEN3600). Composites hydrodynamic size, suspensions polydispersity index (PDI) and composites surface charge (zeta potential; ζ - potential) were measured at 50 and 100 mg / L in 1 mL DTS1061 folded capillary cell (Malvern Instruments). The average hydrodynamic size (Dh) and ζ - potential of each sample was calculated based on three measurements (see respective average values with standard deviation in Table 3.4 in Section 3.3).

DLS is used widely to determine the size distribution of nano- and sub-microscale particles that are subject to Brownian motion. A coherent light from laser beam illuminates the suspension with small particles and the results are determined from the variations of light scattering from the particles. With this method, particles with upper limit 1 - 3 μm can be measured. [38]

Polydispersity Index (PDI) is a parameter that defines the particle size distribution. This value can vary from 0,01 to 1, where 0,01 are mono dispersed particles and values over 0,7 indicate broad particle size distribution. [39]

Hydrodynamic diameter is defined as the diameter of a perfect sphere that would generate the same hydrodynamic friction as the particle of interest [38]. Zeta potential also is an electric potential of a particle usually expressed in mV and it gives an indication on the stability of a particle. Therefore, if the absolute value of zeta potential is high, the particles will resist agglomeration forces and stay dispersed in the suspension which makes it stable. If the zeta potential absolute value is low, close to zero, particles tend to agglomerate. Zeta potential is also dependant on pH, with increase of latter, zeta potential tends to decrease and vice-versa. [38]

According to the manual Malvern device can give accurate measurements for nanosized particles. Nanocomposites that have agglomerated to larger particles may show inaccurate results.

2.5 Toxicity screening with *Vibrio fischeri*

Toxicity screening was performed with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* bioassay using two endpoints:

- 1) inhibition of bioluminescence (modified Flash assay; Subsection 2.5.1) and
- 2) colony-forming ability on nutrient agar plates (a Spot assay; Subsection 2.5.2).

Experimental part of nanocomposite materials toxicity tests with *V. fischeri* was conducted in January – May 2021.

The bacterial suspension used for the toxicity measurements was prepared from freeze-dried bacteria originating from *V. fischeri* reagent (Aboatox Oy, Turku, Finland) (See Figure 2.2). All the chemicals and their dilutions were prepared in 2 % NaCl. A small jar of lyophilized *V. fischeri* bacterial culture pellet stored at -20 °C was dehydrated with the diluent (containing 20 g NaCl, 2,035 g MgCl₂ · 6H₂O and 0,3 g KCl per 1 L of water) and stabilised first at 4 °C for 30 minutes and then at room temperature for another 30 minutes before testing (cell concentration about ~10⁶ cells / mL).

Figure 2.2 A – Lyophilised *Vibrio fischeri* bacteria and its rehydration in the reagent bottle; B – *Vibrio fischeri* bacteria in daylight on nutrient (BH agar) plate with dilution factors of 10 (five dilutions up to a 10⁵-fold dilution); C - *Vibrio fischeri* bacteria on the same agar plate in the dark.

2.5.1 Kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test – modified Flash assay

Kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test with exposure time of 30 minutes with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* was carried out at the room temperature (~20 °C) in 96-well microplates following the ISO 21338:2010 protocol [33]. The temperature of ~20 °C was used instead of 15 °C as stated in the ISO guideline as most of the luminometers cannot be adjusted below the room temperature. Shortly, 100 µL of nanocomposite materials suspension in 2 % NaCl was pipetted into each well, which was supplemented with 100 µL of bacterial suspension by automatic dispensing in the microplate luminometer testing chamber. The bioluminescence was recorded during the first 15 s after dispensing of the bacterial suspension in each well and once again after 30 min

incubation. The Microplate Luminometer Orion II (Berthold Detection Systems, Pforzheim, Germany; see Figure 2.3), controlled by Simplicity Version 4.2 Software, was used for the dispensing and recording of the luminescence.

Figure 2.3 Microplate luminometer Orion II (Berthold Detection Systems)

All the nanocomposite materials and their dilutions were prepared in 2 % NaCl. All the tests were performed in at least 3 independent experiments in at least two technical parallels and 5 – 7 dilutions per experiment. The controls, both negative (2 % NaCl) and positive (ZnSO_4), were included in each measurement series.

The toxicity of the respective materials was first assessed theoretically and later verified experimentally. Dilutions were initially made in larger increments to find the approximate range of possible toxicity. Later, when the intermediate results were screened and the experiments were repeated with the same materials, adjustments in dilutions were made correspondingly. If at initial concentrations inhibition percentages were too low, higher concentrations were used and vice-versa. The concentrations prepared for the initial screening were as follows:

- 1; 10; 100; 250; 500 and 1000 mg / L for composites;
- 1; 10; 100; 500; 1000; 2000; 2500 mg / L for filtrates and;
- 0,1; 1; 10; 100; 1000 mg / L for precursor salts.

The concentration adjustments made at the intermediate experimental phase allowed for more accurate results from the initially measured EC_{50} values. The EC_{50} value corresponds to the concentration of a chemical which reduces the bioluminescence of

V. fischeri bacteria by 50 % after contact time of 30 min. These values were determined from dose-response curves by the Microsoft Excel REGTOX macro [40] using the log-normal model. Final EC₅₀ values were obtained by including the data from all tests with the same sample and the results are discussed in section 3.5.

Due to the turbidity of tested nanocomposite materials, the maximum values of luminescence during the first 5 seconds of test suspensions were different and depended on concentration (See Figure 2.4). However, as already mentioned, the interference of particle-related turbidity with the luminescence signal does not present a problem in the Flash assay as each sample acts as a reference to itself.

Figure 2.4 Example of the kinetic dose-effect curves of bioluminescence of *Vibrio fischeri* exposed to different concentrations of nanocomposite CaFeZr 6:1:1 within 15 seconds and after 30 minutes of contact time with the bacteria. RLU – relative light units.

Inhibition of bacterial luminescence (INH%) by the analysed test samples was calculated as follows [33]:

$$INH\% = 100 - \frac{IT_{30}}{KF \times IT_0} \times 100 \quad (1.2)$$

$$KF = \frac{IC_{30}}{IC_0}, \quad (1.3)$$

where $INH\%$ – percentage of inhibition of bacterial bioluminescence, %,

KF – correction factor, characterises the natural loss of luminescence of the control (i.e. bacterial suspension in 2 % NaCl),

IC_{30} – the respective luminescence values of control after 30 minutes,

IC_0 – the maximum values of luminescence during first 5 seconds after dispensing 100 μ l of test bacteria to 100 μ l of control,

IT_{30} – the respective luminescence values of test sample after 30 minutes,

IT_0 – the maximum values of luminescence during first 5 seconds after dispensing 100 μ l of test bacteria to 100 μ l of test sample.

Graphical results are represented in subsection 3.4.1 and final conclusions on the environmental safety assessment with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* modified Flash test are discussed in section 3.5.

2.5.2 Viability assay – a Spot Test

V. fischeri viability assay was performed as described previously in Suppi et al. 2015 [41] to evaluate the ability of the toxicant exposed bacteria to form colonies on toxicant-free nutrient agar after exposure to the tested chemicals in 2 % NaCl and determine the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC). MBC is the lowest tested concentration

of nanocomposite sorbents which completely inhibited the formation of visible colonies after plating on toxicant-free agar nutrient plates.

Briefly, at the end of the kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test microplates were incubated at room temperature for 2 and 24 hours without shaking in the dark. After 2 h and 24 h of exposure, 3 μ L of the cell suspension from each microplate well was pipetted as a spot onto an agarized *Beneckeia harvey* (BH) growth medium (containing yeast extract 3 g, tryptone 5 g, glycerol, 99 % 2 mL, NaCl 30 g, Na₂HPO₄ · 12H₂O 9,45 g, KH₂PO₄ 1 g, (NH₄)₂HPO₄ 0,5 g, MgSO₄ · 7H₂O 0,3 g, and agar 15 g per 1 L of DI water). The inoculated agar plates were incubated at room temperature for two days until the growth of bacteria was visible. The colonies were visually analysed in the dark when bacteria started to emit light (See Figure 2.4). Each test was repeated 3 times. All test results were photographed and stored. The results of the Spot tests are discussed in Section 3.4.2.

Figure 2.4 A - microplate with turbid nanocomposite samples, B and C - 3 μ l of bacterial suspension exposed to nanocomposite materials from microplate was transferred onto toxicant-free agar plate after 2 h and 24 h incubation time and colonies of luminescent bacteria were visually analysed after 48 hours in the dark, respectively. Numbers 1 - 4 and Zn represent each two test parallels of different tested materials. Red crosses represent MBC values, i.e. no bacterial growth was detected at these test concentrations.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All industrial chemicals introduced should be evaluated for their potential harmful effects to human health and the environment. In the EU, the main acts regulating chemical safety are REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals; [42]) and CLP (Classification, Labelling and Packaging; [43]) Regulation. As a rule, an environmental safety of industrial chemicals is analysed using toxicity tests with algae, daphnia and fish but also bacteria, i.e. representatives of different trophic levels. Bacteria as decomposers are not only the important members of the natural food-webs but also the most suitable test organisms for rapid screening of chemicals' toxic potency, due to the ease of handling in the laboratory and cost-efficiency [22], [44]. In the current thesis, 10 nanocomposite materials were studied with the focus on the test system using naturally luminescent gram-negative bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. Also, physicochemical characterization of the nanocomposite materials was performed using dynamic light scattering method, settling test and total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy. Results of the conducted experiments on the 10 nanocomposite materials, their filtrates and precursor salts are presented and discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Free settling characteristics of nanocomposite materials

Nanocomposite settling characteristics were assessed in DI water and *V. fischeri* test media (2 % NaCl solution). Free settling test results of nanocomposite materials in DI water and 2 % NaCl are presented in the Tables 3.1 and 3.2.

Previous studies [45], [46] have shown that test media, where metal-containing nanomaterials (e.g. ZnO, CuO and Ag nanoparticles) are dispersed may influence their dissolution and consequently, the test results. Test media may contain different organic and inorganic components – ligands, which form complexes with the metal ions. The solubility of nanomaterials as well as stability of suspensions depends on their interactions with compounds of test environment (e.g. amino acids, proteins, natural organic matter etc). NCs may become remarkably unstable and precipitate in mineral media. In contrast, the components of the complex organic rich test media are able to coat and disperse nanomaterials which would prevent their sedimentation. [45]

In the current study, the majority of the tested suspensions of the composites were colourful and turbid, and tended to settle faster in the 2 % NaCl solution than in the deionised water (see Tables 3.1 and 3.2). Taking a look at the first sample ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1 at the highest concentration 1000 mg / L, it can be seen that it has a small precipitate in DI water at the bottom starting from 30 min. The amount of the precipitate is not increasing until the end of the test in DI water (24 h picture). On the other hand, in saline solution much more sediment formation can be observed for the same sample and concentration. Again, the sediment is formed already at 30 min and remains similar until the end of the experiment. The same phenomenon can be observed with all the samples at the highest concentrations in Table 3.1 and with CaZnFeZr 3:1:1:1 from Table 3.2. Similar phenomenon can be observed in Table 3.2 with MgZnFe 1:1:1, where sedimentation occurs at the highest tested concentration at 4 hours for deionised water and within 30 min in 2 % NaCl solution.

According to these observations, an assumption can be made that samples with Zn in their composition tend to stay in suspension in deionised water but settle quickly in 2 % NaCl solution. The addition of Mg and Ca to the material structure makes the composite to settle quickly also in deionised water.

If ZnFeZr are present in the composite then they seem to reduce the precipitation and keep the composite dispersed in deionised water. Addition of Ca to ZnFeZr does not affect the stability of the composite which remains in suspension, as seen in Table 3.2 for composite CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 at the higher tested concentration in deionised water.

Composites with different composition than ZnFeZr seem to settle quickly also in deionised water. This conclusion is made based on the pictures of the highest concentrations in deionised water for composites CaFe 2:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1 and MgFeZr 6:1:1 in Table 3.2.

Observing the highest tested concentrations in Table 3.2 for composites MgFeZr 6:1:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1, variations in the way they agglomerate in different media is noticed. Faster agglomeration and settling is observed in the 2 % NaCl solution compared to DI water, possibly due to the increased ionic strength in the salt media and a shift in the surface charge of the nanocomposites.

To sum up, according to the data in Tables 3.1 and 3.2, the following assumptions could be made on examined samples. The analysed composites:

1. are initially turbid and colourful in both, DI water and 2 % NaCl media;
2. stay relatively stable in deionised water up to 24 hours for ZnFeZr composites and nanocomposite CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 and up to 4 hours for composite MgFeZr 1:1:1;
3. agglomerate quickly (within 30 min) in 2 % NaCl solution;
4. are out of the nano-range due to the fast (30 min) sedimentation observed for all the samples in 2 % NaCl solution and majority of the samples in deionised water. Exception is observed for ZnFeZr composites and CaZnFeZr, where no sedimentation is recognized in deionised water. This could possibly indicate that these samples stay rather in the nano-range;
5. CaFe 2:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1 and MgZnFe 6:1:1 settle quickly in deionised water
6. agglomerate differently according to the media they are suspended in. This was noticed for composites MgFeZr 6:1:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1.

Table 3.1 Settling test and visualisation of stability of the ZnFeZr nanocomposites in DI water and 2 % NaCl. Composites suspensions in deionised water and 2 % NaCl media, at concentrations from 1 to 1000 mg / L. Pictures were taken at 4 time points: 0 min, 30 min, 4 h and 24 h.

	ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1						ZnFeZr 4:1:1						ZnFeZr 6:1:1						ZnFeZr 10:1:1						ZnFeZr 18:5:1					
Deionised water (medium for the stock suspensions of NC materials)																														
mg / L	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1
0 min																														
30 min																														
4 h																														
24 h																														
2 % NaCl solution (testing medium for the <i>V. fischeri</i> assay)																														
0 min																														
30 min																														
4 h																														
24 h																														

Table 3.2 Settling test and visualisation of stability of the CaFe, CaFeZr, CaZnFeZr, MgFeZr and MgZnFe nanocomposites in DI water and 2 % NaCl. Composites suspensions in deionised water and 2 % NaCl media at concentrations from 1 to 1000 mg / L. Pictures were taken at 4 time points: 0 min, 30 min, 4 h and 24 h.

	CaFe 2:1						CaFeZr 6:1:1						CaZnFeZr 3:1:1:1						MgFeZr 6:1:1						MgZnFe 1:1:1											
Deionised water (medium for the stock suspensions of NC materials)																																				
mg / L	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1	1000	500	250	100	10	1
0 min																																				
30 min																																				
4 h																																				
24 h																																				
2 % NaCl solution (testing medium for the <i>V. fischeri</i> assay)																																				
0 min																																				
30 min																																				
4 h																																				
24 h																																				

3.2 Metal concentrations in nanocomposite filtrates

Dissolution of metallic nanoparticles is highly important in the context of metal based NCs toxicity analysis. Metal ion release is one key factor for understanding metallic NCs toxicity and is essential for interpretation of any toxicological study. [47]

According to the analysed data with the Picofox, the metal concentrations detected in the filtrates of all composite materials, including ZnFeZr on MPs, are listed in Table 3.3. All listed metal concentrations are average values of duplicated measurements with standard deviations in the +/- 5 % range. In a couple of cases the analyses were repeated 3 - 4 times and in the case of ZnFeZr on MPs only once. The number of measurements for each sample is listed in the last column of the table.

The highest amount of dissolved zinc was observed for the composite CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 with the concentration of 45,79 mg / L. Second and third highest concentrations of dissolved zinc are observed to be for ZnFeZr 6:1:1 (37,32 mg / L) and ZnFeZr 4:1:1 (21,50 mg / L), respectively. The least amount of zinc was leached from composite MgZnFe 1:1:1 (0,08 mg / L). This could mean that addition of magnesium may be able to prevent the release of zinc ions into the media which needs to be verified by future investigations. On the other hand, low amounts of dissolved zinc might be due to the absence of zirconium. It could be assumed that the presence of zirconium contributes to the leaching of zinc into the test media.

Composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 and the same composite deposited onto magnetic particles (ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs) show a difference in dissolved zinc concentrations. ZnFeZr 6:1:1 has zinc concentration of 37,32 mg / L and ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs only 2,19 mg / L of dissolved zinc. This could mean that magnetic particles make the composite more stable and thus less zinc is leached from the particles. Nevertheless, it should be taken into account that the magnetic composite consists of 80 wt% magnetic carrier particles (magnetite Fe_3O_4) and only 20 wt% of its mass is the active sorbent nanocomposite ZnFeZr 6:1:1, i.e. the stock suspension of the magnetic composites contained 5 times less ZnFeZr than the stock suspension of the pure nanocomposite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 which also explains the higher dissolved Zn value in the latter case.

According to the data in Table 3.3, leached iron concentrations are fairly low, varying between 0,09 - 0,21 mg / L. The molar fraction of iron in the composition of all investigated materials is generally much lower than the molar fraction of Zn, and thus stoichiometrically right, so that all the iron present in the system reacts completely and

forms stable precipitates within the structure of the nanocomposites, which prevents its dissolution into the medium.

Compared to other metals, calcium leached the most in relatively high amounts 22,79 – 33,48 mg / L into the deionised water from all composites which contain it. Thus, it must be taken into account that Ca does not bind efficiently into the nanocomposite structure and these theoretical nominal values of the dosed metals must be verified with a measurement of the actual precipitated metal molar ratios. This, however, was not within the scope of the current thesis and will be performed in the future by the main supervisor Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan. Nevertheless, the presence of dissolved calcium is not expected to increase the toxicity of the particles.

Most Fe (0,21 mg / L) was leached from the ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs (see Table 3.3) which is in compliance with the fact that the magnetic nanocomposite consists mostly of Fe-containing magnetite (Fe₃O₄) nanoparticles core (80 wt%) and only 20 wt% is the active adsorbent ZnFeZr 6:1:1 coating.

Table 3.3: Dissolved metal concentrations in the filtrates of 2 g / L nanocomposite suspensions in deionized water; nd – not detected. Remark: All samples were filtered through a 0,1 µm membrane syringe filter.

Composite	Metal concentration [mg / L]					Number of measurements [n]
	Ca	Fe	Zn	Zr	Mg	
ZnFeZr 18:5:1	-	0,15	13,49	nd	-	2
ZnFeZr 10:1:1	-	0,10	7,16	nd	-	2
ZnFeZr 6:1:1	-	0,18	37,32	nd	-	4
ZnFeZr 4:1:1	-	0,09	21,50	nd	-	2
ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	-	0,11	10,02	nd	-	3
CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	22,79	0,14	45,79	nd	-	2
MgZnFe 1:1:1	-	0,09	0,08	-	nd	2
CaFeZr 6:1:1	30,25	0,08	-	nd	-	2
MgFeZr 6:1:1	-	0,10	-	nd	nd	2
CaFe 2:1	33,48	0,12	-	-	-	2
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs	-	0,21	2,19	nd	-	1

Neither magnesium, nor zirconium was detected in any of the samples during all the experiments. This could mean that Mg and Zr are properly immobilized within the structure of the NCs containing these two metals.

As already discussed in the Section 3.1, composites agglomerate and their settling ability varies depending on the media they are exposed to. Similarly, the medium may affect the dissolved metal content of the composites, which might be different in deionised water compared to 2 % NaCl solution. Further research is essential to gain data on dissolved metal content for filtrates from 2 % NaCl composite stock suspensions.

To sum up, following assumptions and conclusions can be made:

1. Composites do not leach any Zr and Mg and relatively low concentrations of dissolved Fe were observed.
2. Composites containing Zn were confirmed to have dissolved Zn in the deionised water solution. Thus, zinc is expected to be one of the main causes for the toxicity of the studied nanocomposite materials.
3. Composites containing Ca are leaching it in relatively high amounts, leading to the conclusions that Ca is not efficiently incorporated into the structure of the nanocomposites, even though not considered to pose any toxicity risk.
4. Composite MgZnFe 1:1:1 has exceptionally low concentration of dissolved Zn. It is assumed that the presence of Mg or the absence of Zr contributes to the stable incorporation and immobilisation of Zn into the material structure.
5. When the composite is immobilised onto magnetic particles, it was proven to be much more stable and leach significantly less Zn in the suspension. This lowers the concern of particle toxicity and verifies the safe application of the magnetic adsorbent particles in the wastewater treatment field.

3.3 Hydrodynamic size and surface charge of nanocomposites

Nanocomposite materials characteristics, the hydrodynamic diameter (D_h), surface charge (ζ - potential) and heterogeneity (polydispersity index, PDI) in DI water were characterised by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS) at 50 or 100 mg / L (Table 3.4).

Table 3.4 Characterization of nanocomposite suspensions with Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS) in DI water. Hydrodynamic size (Dh), polydispersity index (PDI) and surface charge (ζ - potential) were determined (AVG \pm STDEV).

Composite	Concentration [mg / L]	Hydrodynamic diameter [nm]	Polydispersity Index	Z - potential [mV]
ZnFeZr 18:5:1	50	256 \pm 2,5	0,276 \pm 0,015	27,2 \pm 0,76
ZnFeZr 10:1:1	50	716 \pm 32	0,610 \pm 0,037	13,7 \pm 1,4
ZnFeZr 6:1:1	50	1713 \pm 57	0,364 \pm 0,055	9,2 \pm 0,12
ZnFeZr 6:1:1	100	2637 \pm 155	0,544 \pm 0,085	8,3 \pm 0,33
ZnFeZr 4:1:1	50	376 \pm 32	0,687 \pm 0,024	14,6 \pm 2,8
ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	50	658 \pm 180	0,716 \pm 0,028	8,3 \pm 0,06
CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	50	2049 \pm 486	0,914 \pm 0,081	9,5 \pm 0,05
MgZnFe 1:1:1	50	186 \pm 1,2	0,189 \pm 0,033	27,7 \pm 0,64
CaFeZr 6:1:1	50	2445 \pm 239	0,737 \pm 0,143	-9,0 \pm 0,10
MgFeZr 6:1:1	100	4447 \pm 467	0,213 \pm 0,098	-12,2 \pm 0,38
CaFe 2:1	50	9406 \pm 474	0,562 \pm 0,172	9,2 \pm 0,99

According to the DLS methodology, acceptable values for particle characterization can be obtained for particles whose hydrodynamic diameter (Dh) values are up to 3000 nm (i.e. 3 μ m). All ten studied materials were assumed to be in the nano- or lower micro-range by synthesis, therefore the DLS method was initially chosen for their characterization. During the measurements, however, it was found that some particles were out of the nano-range and fell rather into the middle micro-range, probably due to agglomeration effects. Therefore, the results for MgFeZr 6:1:1 and CaFe 2:1 cannot be considered as representative and other methods must be taken into account for the characterization of these composites. This task, however, is not in the scope of the current thesis due to technical restrictions and time limitations.

PDI values of studied NCs in DI water were observed to be between 0,189 and 0,914. For composites MgZnFe 1:1:1, MgFeZr 6:1:1 and ZnFeZr 18:5:1 PDI values were less than 0,3 indicating a more monodisperse distribution [39] of the particles in the NCs suspensions. Remaining NCs had PDI > 0,3, with the highest value of 0,9 for CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1, suggesting that the suspensions were more polydisperse and were having an inhomogeneous particle size distribution within the sample.

The average Dh of nanocomposite particles is shown in Table 3.4. Five composites (ZnFeZr 18:5:1, ZnFeZr 10:1:1, ZnFeZr 4:1:1, ZnFeZr 3.6:0.2:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1) were observed to be in the nano-range, having Dh values from 186 to 716 nm. According to the measurements, composite MgZnFe 1:1:1 has the smallest Dh of $186 \pm 1,2$ nm, followed by ZnFeZr 18:5:1 with Dh $256 \pm 2,5$ nm and ZnFeZr 4:1:1 with Dh 376 ± 32 nm.

The other five samples (ZnFeZr 6:1:1, CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1, MgFeZr 6:1:1 and CaFe 2:1) were observed to be in the micro-range with Dh values between 1713 for 50 mg / L concentration of composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 and up to 9406 nm for composite CaFe 2:1. As seen also from the settling tests, composites CaFe 2:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1 and MgFeZr 6:1:1 settled quickly in deionised water, which is in accordance with the particle size measurements with the Malvern device. Therefore, an assumption can be made that these three samples have agglomerated with a resulting particle size in the micro-range.

On one hand, composite MgZnFe 1:1:1 remained relatively stable (up to 4 hours) in DI water during the free settling tests. The same nanocomposite has the lowest Dh which verifies its high stability and low settling characteristics. Furthermore, the ZnFeZr composites, which showed relatively high stability in DI water during the free settling tests, are partially in the nano-range according to the Malvern results. On the other hand, the nanocomposite CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 showed high stability in the free settling test although it had a very high PDI value (0,914) and particle size distribution in the micro-range (Dh 2049 nm).

Majority of the NCs surface charges (ζ - potential) were positive (8 - 27 mV), except for CaFeZr 6:1:1 (-9 mV) and MgFeZr 6:1:1 (-12 mV). According to the obtained zeta potential values, composites ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1 were most stable, both having zeta potential around 27 mV. Additionally, their PDI values were below 0,3 and Dh 256 nm and 186 nm respectively. Thus, it can be concluded that these two composites are the most stable [39] among all ten.

Based on the results of the dissolved metal content, it can be concluded that there is not necessarily a correlation between the stability of the particles in terms of agglomeration and the dissolution of metals from the particle structure. This can be noticed with both composites ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1, which were proven to be very stable against agglomeration, but the first one ZnFeZr 18:5:1 had a relatively

high dissolved Zn concentration of 13,49 mg / L, and the second one a very low dissolved Zn concentration of 0,08 mg / L.

To sum up, the following conclusions can be drawn from the DLS results:

1. The particle size distribution of the composites MgFeZr 6:1:1 and CaFe 2:1 is out of the measuring range for Malvern Nanosizer and thus the results are disputable and must be verified with another analytical method.
2. The size distribution of samples ZnFeZr 6:1:1, CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 and CaFeZr 6:1:1 is in the lower micro-range.
3. Composites ZnFeZr 18:5:1, ZnFeZr 10:1:1, ZnFeZr 4:1:1, ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1 are with particle size in the nano-range.
4. Composites ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and MgZnFe 1:1:1 have the highest absolute values of zeta potential (27,2 and 27,7 mV respectively) which means that they are stable nanocomposites.
5. No correlation was found between the agglomeration stability of the composites and their dissolved Zn content.

3.4 Toxicity screening with *Vibrio fischeri*

In the current study, new toxicological data were provided for a set of nanocomposites as these compounds have not been analysed for the toxicity using *V. fischeri*. Results of the nanocomposites from the 30 min bacterial bioluminescence inhibition assay and viability test (2 h and 24 h) are presented in Subsections 3.4.1 and 3.4.2, respectively.

Summarising discussion on the environmental safety is followed in the Section 3.5.

3.4.1 Kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test – modified Flash assay

The kinetic *V. fischeri* luminescence inhibition assay is an ISO standardized acute toxicity test (ISO 21338, 2010, [33]). This test is a very rapid, simple, cost effective and sensitive method to screen and evaluate toxic properties of different chemical substances (including nanomaterials) by measuring the reduction of light production

due to interactions between bacteria and toxic compounds [2], [44], [48]. The following graphs depict dose-response curves for kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test for the studied composites, their filtrates, precursor salts, ZnFeZr 6:1:1 deposited on magnetic particles, its filtrate and positive control (ZnSO_4) (Figures 3.1 - 3.4). The 30 min EC_{50} values (mg / L) of the composite material could be calculated for 8 out of 11 composites (the tested concentrations for NCs varied from 1 to 2500 mg / L) and ranged from 36,9 mg / L for ZnFeZr 18:5:1 to 1123 mg / L for ZnFeZr 6:1:1 deposited on MPs. In case of two composites (ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and ZnFeZr 10:1:1) 30 min EC_{50} values for *V. fischeri* were < 100 mg / L. Since most of the composite materials include Zn as one of their components, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was selected as a positive control in the current study. Zinc sulphate heptahydrate is also recommended as one of the reference substances according to the ISO standard (ISO 21338, 2010 [33]). The average 30 min EC_{50} value for $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (as Zn^{2+}) throughout the experiments was 7,8 mg / L which is in accordance with the value given in the standard ISO 21338, 2010 [33].

It is known that the solubilised Zn ions in aqueous environment are the main contributor to Zn-based nanomaterials toxicity ([2], [49]). Thus, the Zn fractions in mass percentage were calculated for all NCs and listed in Table 3.5 in order to investigate further the correlation between the Zn content, respectively the release of its ions, and the obtained toxicological response of the studied NCs.

According to the Table 3.5 The nominal zinc mass varies from 33 % (ZnFeZr 10:1:1) to 6 % (ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs) among the NCs. ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs has significantly less zinc in the composition due to the fact that the ZnFeZr fraction is only 20 wt% of the whole composite mass and the rest 80 wt% is the carrier magnetite-silica matrix. Highest toxicity (EC_{50} 10,5 mg / L) based on Zn^{2+} was observed for ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and lowest (EC_{50} 62,9 mg / L) for ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs. The material ZnFeZr 18:5:1 has the highest toxicity effect (lowest EC_{50} value) although it has 4% less zinc in its composition compared to ZnFeZr 10:1:1 with the highest Zn fraction of 33 wt%. Highest EC_{50} value can be explained by the difference in leached zinc (13,49 mg / L for ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and 7,16 mg / L for ZnFeZr 10:1:1; See Table 3.3). CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 was the second by toxicity effect (EC_{50} 15,3 mg / L normalized by Zn^{2+}) but had relatively low (14 wt%) zinc in its composition and the highest value of leached zinc (45,79 mg / L; See Table 3.3). As hypothesised, higher amounts of leached zinc increase the toxicological response to the NCs and vice versa: MgZnFe 1:1:1 and ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs have the lowest toxicological responses based on ionic Zn^{2+} (EC_{50} 52,1 mg / L and 62,9 mg / L respectively) and they leached the least Zn (0,08 mg / L and 2,19 mg / L respectively; see Table 3.3). ZnFeZr 18:5:1 EC_{50} value of 10,5 mg / L normalized by ionic Zn^{2+} is on

the borderline to be classified as toxic (toxic if $EC_{50} < 10$ mg / L) and should not be considered as a viable option for commercial use.

Table 3.5 Zn fraction in mass percentage of the studied NCs and the respective EC_{50} values calculated based on ionic Zn (Zn^{2+}). Remarks: Nominal mass values were used for the calculations. The calculation of the EC_{50} values of the whole composite are presented later in this section and just summarized here for convenience. The composite materials in this table are listed in ascending order of the EC_{50} values by Zn^{2+} .

Composite name	Mass of Zn^{2+} [g]	Molar mass of the NCs [g]	Zn fraction in mass percentage	EC_{50} value of the whole composite [mg / L]	EC_{50} value based only on Zn^{2+} [mg / L]
ZnFeZr 18:5:1	1177	4127	29 %	36,86	10,5
CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	196	1442	14 %	112,5	15,3
ZnFeZr 10:1:1	654	1955	33 %	53,91	18,0
ZnFeZr 4:1:1	262	1138	23 %	118,8	27,3
ZnFeZr 6:1:1	392	1410	28 %	118	32,8
ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	235	867	27 %	168,2	45,7
MgZnFe 1:1:1	65	610	11 %	485,8	52,1
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs	392	1410	6 %	1123	62,9

The obtained dose-response curves of the tested nanocomposites towards *V. fischeri* are presented in the Figures 3.1-3.4. The complete experimental data for the plots in these graphs can be found in the appendix section (Appendices 1-3). Remark: each graph (Figure 3.1-3.4) includes a horizontal dashed 50 % inhibition line. This does not correspond directly to the EC_{50} value as these graphs are dose-response curves and EC_{50} values were obtained by macro REGTOX [40] *via* complex fitting curves.

As seen from the Figure 3.1 two of the NCs are in the harmful range (EC_{50} 10 – 100 mg / L, see simplified hazard classification scheme given in Section 3.5): highest toxicological effect ($EC_{50} = 36,86$ mg / L) was measured for ZnFeZr 18:5:1 (red dashed line) and second for ZnFeZr 10:1:1 (brown dashed line) with $EC_{50} = 53,91$ mg / L. Other composites show response at concentrations > 100 mg / L and are therefore not classified / not harmful. Decreasing toxicological effect can be observed for ZnFeZr NCs from left to right, in correlation with the nominal Zn molar ratios of these five ZnFeZr composites. However, the EC_{50} values normalized by zinc (to ionic Zn^{2+}) are lower than the original EC_{50} values (see Table 3.5) and fall into the harmful range for all seven NCs but the order of toxicity stays almost compliant with the original EC_{50} values for the whole composites. The most significant shift in EC_{50} value was observed for CaZnFeZr

3:3:1:1 from original $EC_{50} = 112,5 \text{ mg / L}$ to Zn-normalized $EC_{50} = 15,3 \text{ mg / L}$ which shifts the material classification to the more concerning "harmful" range.

Figure 3.1 Dose-response curves of seven nanocomposite materials and the positive control ($ZnSO_4$, as Zn^{2+}) and their EC_{50} values towards bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. Remark: The X-axis is in the logarithmic scale.

In Figure 3.2 dose-response curves of the filtrates of the same seven NCs are presented. It can be observed that the filtrates have an effect of one magnitude lower EC_{50} values than the same composite materials (see Figures 3.1 and 3.2). The EC_{50} values for the filtrates range from 490,1 mg / L (CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1) to 2011 mg / L (ZnFeZr 10:1:1). Additionally, MgZnFe 1:1:1 filtrate EC_{50} value was not detected in tested concentration range (up to 2500 mg / L), which can be explained by the very low value of leached zinc in the filtrate (0,08 mg / L; See Table 3.3).

Figure 3.2 Dose-response curves of seven filtrates of nanocomposites and the positive control (ZnSO_4 , as Zn^{2+}) and their EC_{50} values towards bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. Remarks: nd - no EC_{50} value was determined (at the highest concentration tested the luminescence inhibition was < 50 %). The X-axis is in the logarithmic scale.

The Zn fraction in mass percentage for all tested NCs filtrates and the Zn-containing precursor salt ZnCl_2 , including all EC_{50} values, are summarized in Table 3.6 and ordered by ascending EC_{50} values normalized by Zn^{2+} , analogically to Table 3.5. It can be observed that only CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 (EC_{50} based on Zn^{2+} 66,7 mg / L) is considered as harmful (EC_{50} value between 10 – 100 mg / L) due to the highest value of leached zinc (45,79 mg / L; See Table 3.3). EC_{50} values of the precursor salt ZnCl_2 and the positive control ZnSO_4 based on ionic Zn^{2+} are similar: 8,4 mg / L and 7,78 mg / L, respectively. All other ZnFeZr based NCs have normalized EC_{50} values > 100 mg / L and are therefore not classified in terms of hazard ranking.

Table 3.6 The Zn fraction in mass percentage of the studied NCs filtrates plus Zn precursor salt (ZnCl_2) and their respective EC_{50} values calculated based on ionic Zn (Zn^{2+}). Remark: Nominal mass values were used for the calculations. The material filtrates in this table are listed in ascending order of the EC_{50} values by Zn^{2+} .

Filtrate name	Mass of Zn^{2+} [g]	Molar mass of the NCs [g]	Zn fraction in mass percentage	EC_{50} value of the whole filtrate [mg / L]	EC_{50} value based only on Zn^{2+} [mg / L]
ZnCl_2 (precursor salt)	65	136	48%	17,47	8,4
CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	196	1442	14%	490,1	66,7
ZnFeZr 6:1:1	392	1410	28%	799	222
ZnFeZr 4:1:1	262	1138	23%	1002	230
ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	235	867	27%	1395	379
ZnFeZr 18:5:1	1177	4127	29%	1643	469
ZnFeZr 10:1:1	654	1955	33%	2011	673

In Figure 3.3 the dose-response curves of the precursor salt solutions are depicted. The Fe and Zr salts had the highest toxicity with EC_{50} values 1,22 and 2,20 mg / L, respectively. However, the pH values of the salt solutions were too low, pH 1,9 for $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and pH 1,8 for $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and thus outside the optimal range pH 6-8,5 for tests with *V. fischeri* according to ISO standard, meaning that the toxicity effect of these salts was rather caused by the extremely acidic pH values and adjustment of the pH was necessary. In the current study, however, no testing with adjusted pH of precursor salts was carried out because the pH adjustment with NaOH caused the formation of solid precipitates in the Fe- and Zr-containing salt solutions and made the reliable testing of these samples practically impossible. Other methods to adjust the pH and keep the salt in solution need to be examined further before any toxicity tests can be performed, but this was out of scope of the current thesis work. From the other tested precursor salts, the ZnCl_2 (orange dotted line) showed high toxicity, as expected, with $\text{EC}_{50} = 17,47$ mg / L. From the literature it is known that the solubilised metal ions (e.g. Zn, Cu, Ag) leached from (nano)particles are the main contributor to the toxicity of nanomaterials [47], [2]. Mg and Ca salts were not toxic to *V. fischeri*, which is in agreement with the literature data [49] and also supported by the fact that Mg is one of the important nutrients for bacteria *V. fischeri* present in the agar medium.

Figure 3.3 Dose-response curves of five precursor salt solutions and the positive control (ZnSO_4 , as Zn^{2+}) and their EC_{50} values towards bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. Remarks: nd - no EC_{50} value was determined (the luminescence inhibition was < 50 % at the highest tested concentration). The X-axis is in the logarithmic scale.

The following Figure 3.4 summarizes the dose-response curves for all the samples (precursors, composites and their filtrates) associated with the material ZnFeZr 6:1:1, including its magnetized version (ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs), which is the most promising material with highest efficiency for phosphorus recovery among all other tested composites.

It can be clearly seen that the precursor salt has the highest toxicological response followed by the composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1, its filtrate, ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs and its filtrate. This graph is a good demonstration of the successful reduction in toxicity during the engineering process of the adsorbent materials. According to Tables 3.5 and 3.6, the Zn-normalized EC_{50} values of the composite and its filtrate changed from 32,8 mg / L for the solid composite to 222 mg / L for its filtrate (0,1 μm) containing only the

dissolved ionic fraction of the filtered material. For the composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs it changed from 62,9 mg / L to not detectable value (tested range up to 5000 mg / L) for its respective filtrate, meaning that there should not be any concerns in terms of hazardous effects for the actual application of the magnetic adsorbent in the real wastewater treatment process, because the magnetic adsorbent particles do not leach any toxic substances in their filtrate.

Figure 3.4 Dose-response curves and EC₅₀ values of the most efficient and favourable sample for phosphorus recovery ZnFeZr 6:1:1 and its variations (composite and composite on MPs, their filtrates, Zn precursor salt and positive control: ZnSO₄). Remarks: nd - no EC₅₀ value was determined (the luminescence inhibition was < 50 % at the highest tested concentration). The X-axis is in the logarithmic scale.

3.4.2 Viability assay – a Spot Test

In the current study, the viability of bacterial cells exposed to NCs was estimated using the Spot assay introduced in the “Materials and methods” Section 2.5.2. The bioluminescence inhibition of *V. fischeri* caused by toxicants is a sub-lethal response and does not fully reflect the viability of cells. The minimum bactericidal concentration

(MBC) is based on the viability / mortality endpoint, i.e. the inability of the cells to grow after exposure to a toxic concentration of the composite.

MBC values for composites, their filtrates and precursor salts towards *V. fischeri* are presented in Tables 3.7 - 3.10.

Table 3.7 depicts the viability assay test data for all ten nanocomposites. It can be observed that none of the composites were toxic enough to have 2 h MBC value. All Zn containing composites (except for MgZnFe 1:1:1 – no MBC value detected at tested concentrations) had 24 h MBC values ranging from 100 - 250 mg / L. For composites that have no Zn in their structure, MBC values at tested concentrations could not be determined.

Regarding the different precursor salts used for the synthesis of the adsorbent materials, the 2 h MBC values were higher than the highest tested concentration (2500 mg / L), except for the two precursor salts FeCl₃ and ZrOCl₂ with MBC values 5 mg / L and 10 mg / L, respectively (see Table 3.9) but this was due to the acidic pH values of the samples (pH 1,8 for the Fe salt and pH 1,9 for Zr salt). The 24 h MBC values could be determined for all ZnFeZr-based NCs and the CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 composite, i.e. Zn-containing materials, but not for the MgZnFe 1:1:1.

Based on the solubility data (TXRF analysis) presented earlier in Table 3.3, it is most likely that the toxicity of the Zn-based NCs is due to dissolved zinc. The MgZnFe 1:1:1 was the only NCs which has zinc but did not have an MBC value within the tested concentration range (See Table 3.7). This can be explained with the very low value 0,08 mg / L of leached zinc (see Table 3.3) and the high stability of the MgZnFe 1:1:1 material.

The 24 h MBC values were on average up to 10²-fold higher compared to 30 min EC₅₀ values. Analogous results have been obtained in other studies with lanthanides for example, where *V. fischeri* 24 h MBC values were on average 2-fold higher compared to the 30 min EC₅₀ values [50].

Table 3.7 Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values of 10 nanocomposite materials, contact time 2h and 24h. Remarks: 2 h MBC values are above the tested range (1000 mg / L); nd – not determined.

Composite	2 h contact time								24 h contact time								24 h MBC [mg / L]		
	Concentration [mg / L]								Concentration [mg / L]										
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O as Zn ²⁺ positive control EC ₅₀ = 7,78 mg / L	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50	100	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50	100	50
ZnFeZr 18:5:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 36,86 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	100				
ZnFeZr 10:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 53,91 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	250				
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 118,0 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	250				
ZnFeZr 4:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 118,8 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	100				
ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 168,2 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	250				
CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 112,5 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	250				
MgZnFe 1:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 485,8 mg / L	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	nd				
CaFeZr 6:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = nd	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	nd				
MgFeZr 6:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = nd	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	nd				
CaFe 2:1 composite EC ₅₀ = nd	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	nd				

In Table 3.8 the spot test results for seven filtrates are depicted. An MBC value could be determined only for one NC filtrate after 24 h of incubation, i.e for CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 with 24 h MBC = 2000 mg / L. Slight inhibition in colony forming ability was also observed for ZnFeZr 6:1:1 filtrate at concentrations of 2000 mg / L and higher, however, no MBC value was detected at the tested concentrations. These disruptions can be explained with the relatively high leaching of zinc for CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 and ZnFeZr 6:1:1 with 45,79 mg / L and 37,32 mg / L, respectively (see Table 3.3). For the other nanocomposite filtrates, MBC values after 2 and 24 h incubation could not be determined even at concentrations as high as 2500 mg / L.

Table 3.8 Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values after 2 h and 24 h contact time for the filtrates (pore size 0,1 μm) of the respective nanocomposites. Remarks: 2 h MBC values are above the tested range (2500 mg / L); nd - not determined. The listed concentrations for all nanocomposites correspond to the nominal dry solid concentration of the dosed material before filtration.

Composite	2 h contact time									24 h contact time									24 h MBC [mg / L]	
	Concentration [mg / L]	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50	100	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50		100
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O as Zn ²⁺ positive control EC ₅₀ = 7,78 mg / L																				50
Concentration [mg / L]	C	1	10	100	500	1000	2000	2500		C	1	10	100	500	1000	2000	2500			
ZnFeZr 18:5:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = 1,643 mg / L																				nd
ZnFeZr 10:1:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = 2,011 mg / L																				nd
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = 799,0 mg / L																				nd
ZnFeZr 4:1:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = 1,002 mg / L																				nd
ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = 1,395 mg / L																				nd
CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = 490,1 mg / L																				2000
MgZnFe 1:1:1 filtrate EC ₅₀ = nd																				nd

According to the data in Table 3.9, for the Zn precursor salt (ZnCl_2) the inhibition of the colony forming ability of bacteria *V. fischeri* after 24 h incubation time was noticed to take place at a concentration of 25 mg / L. This is comparable with the results obtained for the positive control chemical (ZnSO_4) where inhibition of the colony forming ability could be observed at the same concentration (25 mg Zn / L) and the 24 h MBC value was 50 mg Zn / L. It could be estimated that the 24 h MBC value for ZnCl_2 would also be around 50 mg / L. The Fe- and Zr-containing precursor salts had both low MBC values (FeCl_3 : 2 h and 24 h MBC values 5 mg / L; ZrOCl_2 : 2 h and 24 h MBC values 10 mg / L) which can be explained again with the highly acidic pH values of the precursor solutions (pH 1,9 and pH 1,8, respectively).

Table 3.9 Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values for the precursor salts of the respective nanocomposites after 2 h and 24 h contact time. Remarks: nd - not determined.

Composite	2 h contact time									2 h MBC [mg / L]	24 h contact time									24 h MBC [mg / L]		
	Concentration [mg / L]	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50		100	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50		100	
$\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as Zn^{2+} positive control $\text{EC}_{50} = 7,78 \text{ mg / L}$											nd											50
Concentration [mg / L]	C	0,1	1	10	100	1000					C	0,1	1	10	100	1000						
$\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Precursor salt $\text{EC}_{50} = \text{nd}$											nd											nd
$\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Precursor salt $\text{EC}_{50} = \text{nd}$											nd											nd
Concentration [mg / L]	C	0,1	1	5	10	100	1000				C	0,1	1	5	10	100	1000					
$\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Precursor salt $\text{EC}_{50} = 1,22 \text{ mg / L}$											5											5
$\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ precursor $\text{EC}_{50} = 2,20 \text{ mg / L}$											10											10
Concentration [mg / L]	C	0,4	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	12,5	25			C	0,4	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	12,5	25				
ZnCl_2 precursor salt $\text{EC}_{50} = \text{nd}$											nd											nd

Table 3.10 summarizes the spot test results for the most promising nanocomposite and most efficient material for phosphorus recovery ZnFeZr 6:1:1, its filtrate and the same composite on MPs and its filtrate. The only MBC value which could be obtained was for the pure composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 at 24 h contact time and it was 24 h MBC = 250 mg / L. Disruptions of the colony forming ability could be observed for the ZnFeZr 6:1:1 supernatant filtrate at concentrations 2000 mg / L and higher. According to the results in Table 3.10, it is evident that the toxicological response to the nanocomposite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 is reduced or even non-existent when the composite is deposited onto magnetic carrier particles (MPs), thus assuring the stability and the safe application of the engineered adsorbent for phosphorus recovery in wastewater treatment.

Table 3.10 Minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) after 2 h and 24 h contact time of all samples associated with the best-performing adsorbent material ZnFeZr 6:1:1: pure ZnFeZr 6:1:1 and its filtrate, ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on magnetic particles and its filtrate, and positive control. Remark: 2 h MBC values are above tested range (2500 mg / L). The listed concentrations for all ZnFeZr-based nanocomposites, including supernatants, correspond to the nominal dry solid concentration of the dosed material before filtration. The concentration units in the last row are purposefully converted to [g / L] to reduce the numbers by a factor of x1000 and save typing space in the limited column widths of the table.

Composite	2 h contact time									24 h contact time									24 h MBC [mg / L]
Concentration [mg / L]	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50	100	C	0,8	1,6	3,2	6,3	13	25	50	100	
ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O as Zn ²⁺ positive control EC ₅₀ = 7,78 mg / L																			50
Concentration [mg / L]	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000					
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 composite EC ₅₀ = 118,0 mg / L															250				
Concentration [mg / L]	C	1	10	100	500	1000	2000	2500	C	1	10	100	500	1000	2000	2500			
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 supernatant EC ₅₀ = 799,0 mg / L																	nd		
Concentration [mg / L]	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000	C	1	10	100	250	500	1000					
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 composite on MPs EC ₅₀ = 1123 mg / L															nd				
Concentration [g / L]	C	0,001	0,1	0,5	1	2	3	4	5	C	0,001	0,1	0,5	1	2	3	4	5	
ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs supernatant EC ₅₀ = nd																			nd

To sum up the data from the testing with the bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, the following conclusions and assumptions can be made:

1. The toxicological response of the tested composites was positively correlated with the presence of Zn in their structure and the solubilised Zn ions leached from the composites;
2. The MBC values for the filtrates of the tested nanocomposites after 2 h and 24 h of incubation could not be determined even at concentrations as high as 2500 mg / L, except for CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 (24 h MBC = 2000 mg / L);
3. Toxicity of the precursor salt ZnCl₂ is similar to the bacterial response to the positive control ZnSO₄;
4. Further experiments need to be performed with neutralized Fe and Zr precursor salt solutions with pH value adjusted in the range pH 6 - 8,5 in order to obtain scientifically relevant data. For this purpose, a complexation method must be found which will keep the pH adjusted salts in solution, without allowing the formation of any solid precipitates;
5. The toxicological response to the nanocomposite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 is reduced significantly by depositing and immobilizing the adsorbent material onto magnetic particles and thus improving its chemical and mechanical stability.

3.5 Hazard ranking of nanocomposites

In this section final conclusions are made on the toxicological response of the studied materials and are summarized in Table 3.11. This table lists all experimentally obtained results (30 min EC₅₀ and 24 h MBC values) and provides a simplified hazard classification scheme [2] for all tested nanocomposite materials according to the testing data of bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*.

Table 3.11 Overview of toxicity results (30 min EC₅₀ and 24 h MBC values) for all nanocomposites (including their filtrates and precursor salts) and NCs and precursor salts ranking according to a simplified hazard classification scheme used in the previous research [44]. Remarks: nd - not determined (at tested concentrations). The listed concentrations for all nanocomposites, including their filtrates, correspond to the nominal dry solid concentration of the dosed material before filtration.

	Composition	30 min EC ₅₀ [mg / L]	95 % confidence interval	24 h MBC [mg / L]
Composites	ZnFeZr 18:5:1	36,86	28,97 - 49,05	100
	ZnFeZr 10:1:1	53,91	40,97 - 69,96	250
	ZnFeZr 6:1:1	118	93,84 - 127	250
	ZnFeZr 4:1:1	118,8	104,8 - 131	100
	ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	168,2	141 - 176,7	250
	CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	112,5	90,9 - 117,8	250
	MgZnFe 1:1:1	485,8	390,5 - 598,4	nd
	CaFeZr 6:1:1	nd	-	nd
	MgFeZr 6:1:1	nd	-	nd
	CaFe 2:1	nd	-	nd
	ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs	1123	928,7 - 1173	nd
Filtrates	ZnFeZr 18:5:1	1643	1407 - 1713	nd
	ZnFeZr 10:1:1	2011	1713 - 2149	nd
	ZnFeZr 6:1:1	799	666,4 - 778,4	nd
	ZnFeZr 4:1:1	1002	853,2 - 983,2	nd
	ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	1395	1218 - 1391	nd
	CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	490,1	424,1 - 491,6	2000
	MgZnFe 1:1:1	nd	-	nd
	ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs	nd	-	nd
Precursor salts	CaCl ₂ · 2H ₂ O	nd	-	nd
	MgCl ₂ · 6H ₂ O	nd	-	nd
	ZnCl ₂	17,47	14,44 - 17,99	nd
	FeCl ₃ · 6H ₂ O	1,22	1,12 - 1,25	5
	ZrOCl ₂ · 8H ₂ O	2,2	2,12 - 2,22	10

Extremely toxic Very toxic Toxic Harmful Not classified

EC₅₀ ≤ 0.1 mg / L 0.1 < EC₅₀ ≤ 1 mg / L 1 < EC₅₀ ≤ 10 mg / L 10 < EC₅₀ ≤ 100 mg / L EC₅₀ > 100 mg / L

Considering that NC suspensions are often turbid due to agglomeration of particles, the kinetic format of the *V. fischeri* test is appropriate for the toxicity screening of NCs. As seen from Table 3.11 tested NCs and their filtrates were generally of low ecotoxicity (30 min EC₅₀ > 100 mg / L). According to the simplified hazard classification scheme, 2 out of 11 NCs were categorised as harmful: ZnFeZr 18:5:1 (30 min EC₅₀ value 36,86 mg / L) and ZnFeZr 10:1:1 (30 min EC₅₀ value 53,91 mg / L).

The toxicological effects of the Zn-based NCs can be explained by the soluble fraction of zinc (values up to 45,79 mg / L for CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1; see Table 3.3). Correlation was observed in Section 3.4.1 between leached Zn values and toxicological effects (Table 3.5 and 3.6). Positive control, Zn salt (ZnSO₄ · 7H₂O), ranked as toxic has a 30 min EC₅₀ value 7,8 mg / L (calculated as Zn²⁺).

When the EC₅₀ values of the tested nanocomposites were normalized by zinc, then the majority of the materials fell into harmful category with EC₅₀ values in the range 10 – 100 mg / L (see Table 3.5). Nevertheless, the exact toxicity mechanisms need to be investigated further in future research and verified if the toxicity effect comes predominantly from the soluble Zn fraction in the materials or if there are other contributing factors to the toxicity mechanisms.

Previous research has shown that from all listed metals, Zn can be toxic to *V. fischeri* even at low concentrations (15 and 30 min EC₅₀ values 0,62 to 5,8 mg Zn²⁺ / L) [23].

The Flash assay data were in general agreement with the spot test: the 30 min EC₅₀ values were by average 100 - fold lower than 24 h MBC values (See Table 3.11). Majority of the tested nanocomposites (e.g. ZnFeZr 10:1:1, MgZnFe 6:1:1 etc.) had 24 h MBC values above the classification threshold (> 100 mg / L) or above the highest tested concentrations. Positive control (ZnSO₄ as Zn²⁺: 24 h MBC value 50 mg / L) as well as some of the Zn-based composites - ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and ZnFeZr 4:1:1 - showed 24 h MBC values in the harmful range: 100 mg / L both.

Some precursor salts used for the particle synthesis have already undergone toxicity classification according to the harmonised classification and labelling system (CLP Regulation, [43]) approved by the EU. According to the harmonised classification in terms of aquatic toxicity and the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) database Information on Chemicals [51], the following statements can be made:

- Zinc chloride (ZnCl_2 , CAS no 7646-85-7¹) is very toxic to the aquatic life (H400) and is very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects (H410). (Short-term toxicity to fish: the lowest LC_{50} values for *Pimephales promelas* 0,33 - 0,78 mg Zn / L; Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates: the lowest EC_{50} values for *Ceriodaphnia dubia* 0,147 - 0,53 mg Zn / L);
- Iron (III) chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, CAS no 10025-77-1²,) and iron trichloride (FeCl_3 , CAS no 7705-08-0³) have no harmonised classification. (Short-term toxicity to fish: LC_{50} value for *Pimephales promelas* 21,8 mg / L; Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates: LC_{50} value for *Daphnia magna* 9,6 mg / L);
- Zirconium (IV) oxychloride octahydrate ($\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, CAS no 7699-43-6⁴) has no harmonised classification. (Short-term toxicity to fish: LC_{50} value for *Pimephales promelas* 17,8 - 239 mg Zr / L; Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates: *Daphnia magna* EC_{50} value > 100 mg Zr / L);
- Magnesium dichloride hexahydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, CAS no 7791-18-6⁵) has no harmonised classification and no ecotoxicological test results available;
- Calcium chloride dihydrate ($\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, CAS no 10043-52-4⁶) has no harmonised classification. (Short-term toxicity to fish: LC_{50} value for *Pimephales promelas* 4630 - 6660 mg / L; Short-term toxicity to aquatic invertebrates: EC_{50} value for *Daphnia magna* 2400 mg / L). [49] [52]

In the current study, Zn precursor salt (ZnCl_2) showed toxic effects (EC_{50} 17,47 mg / L) towards bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* and this is in agreement with the data for aquatic organisms from the ECHA database [52]. The Fe and Zr salts also showed toxic effects but this was rather due to their extreme acidity with pH values < 1,9 and inability to adjust the pH within the neutral range pH 6 - 8,5, which is recommended for the *Vibrio fischeri* tests, without the unwanted precipitates formation. Ca and Mg salts are not toxic for aquatic organisms according to the ECHA data [52] and did not show any toxic effect to *V. fischeri* also in the current research.

¹ <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.028.720>

² <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.122.684>

³ <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.028.846>

⁴ <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.028.835>

⁵ <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.117.877>

⁶ <https://echa.europa.eu/substance-information/-/substanceinfo/100.030.115>

Taking into consideration all test results, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Seven NCs (ZnFeZr 6:1:1, ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1, CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1, MgZnFe 1:1:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1, MgFeZr 6:1:1 and CaFe 2:1) out of ten were ranked as not classified / not harmful towards bacteria *V. fischeri* according to the obtained test results from modified Flash assay and Spot assay (30 min EC₅₀ and 24 h MBC values > 100 mg / L).
2. ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and ZnFeZr 10:1:1 were classified as harmful (30 min EC₅₀ values 36,86 and 53,91 mg / L respectively). The observed harmful effect was mainly explained by the solubilised Zn ions.
3. All of the filtrates from nanocomposites had 30 min EC₅₀ and 24 h MBC values > 100 mg / L towards bacteria *V. fischeri*.
4. Zn precursor salt (ZnCl₂) was classified as harmful (30 min EC₅₀ = 17,47 mg / L; 8,4 mg / L based on Zn²⁺) for the *V. fischeri*, as expected.
5. ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and ZnFeZr 10:1:1 should be reconsidered for commercial application as they have high amounts of Zn mass in their composition (29 % and 33 % respectively) and therefore had the highest toxicity (10,5 mg / L and 18,5 mg / L for ionic Zn²⁺) among the studied NCs.
6. Composite CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1 should also be reconsidered for commercial use as it leached the highest amount (45,79 mg / L) of Zn and therefore had high toxicity (EC₅₀ 15,2 mg / L) normalized by Zn²⁺.
7. According to the ecotoxicological assessment with *V. fischeri* in the current study, the best candidates of NC sorbents for application in phosphorus recovery should not leach high amounts of Zn, neither have high mass percentage of zinc in their composition, although Zn is a necessary element to improve the P-sorption properties of the material. When NCs are deposited on magnetic carriers, their toxicity decreases as their mass percentage within the structure of the composite is reduced significantly (for ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs magnetic carrier is 80 wt% of the total composite, therefore toxicity is reduced from 32,8 to 62,9 mg / L for ionic Zn²⁺). Thus, the most promising candidates for commercial use are ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs, MgZnFe 1:1:1 and NCs not containing any zinc (e.g. CaFeZr 6:1:1, MgFeZr 6:1:1, CaFe 1:1).

SUMMARY

The main problem that the current thesis was addressing – the lack of consistent toxicity data that could be used for the environmental safety assessment on novel NC phosphorus adsorption materials – has been solved by evaluating toxicity of the composites, their filtrates and precursor salts. Results for the toxicity evaluation to bacteria *V. fischeri* are summarized below and discussed in more detail in Chapter 3.

According to the three main outcomes (physicochemical characterization, toxicity screening and identification of possible candidates from the 10 studied nanocomposite sorbent materials for phosphorus recovery) of the main objective, the following statements are giving an overview of the main findings of the thesis:

1. Although the primary size of phosphorus adsorption composites was at the nanoscale, the average hydrodynamic size of the studied materials was rather in the higher nano- / lower micro-range: 186 (ZnFeZr 18:5:1) to 9406 (CaFe 2:1) nm.
2. The *V. fischeri* kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test as a rapid and cost-efficient assay can be recommended for initial (eco)toxicity screening of nanocomposite materials.
3. According to the obtained toxicity data (30 min EC₅₀ and 24 h MBC values, mg / L) of nanocomposite materials for bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*, seven (ZnFeZr 6:1:1, ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1, CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1, MgZnFe 1:1:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1, MgFeZr 6:1:1 and CaFe 2:1) out of ten initial composites were ranked as “not classified / not harmful” (30 min EC₅₀ value and 24 h MBC values above 100 mg / L).
4. Two materials, ZnFeZr 18:5:1 and ZnFeZr 10:1:1, were classified as “harmful” (EC₅₀ 10 - 100 mg / L) with 30 min EC₅₀ values 36,86 mg / L and 53,91 mg / L respectively.
5. The observed toxicological response of Zn-based NCs was mainly explained by the dissolved zinc – further research needs to be undertaken.
6. Based on the results of the current study, the most promising nanocomposite material in terms of environmental safety and phosphorus adsorption efficiency is ZnFeZr 6:1:1 with the EC₅₀ value of 118,0 mg / L and 24 h MBC = 250 mg / L.

The author suggests further investigation of the potential environmental hazards of seven Zn-based nanocomposite materials to the aquatic ecosystem by using model organisms from different trophic levels in the aquatic food-web (i.e algae and crustaceans). Furthermore, toxicity testing of precursor salts with adjusted pH should be further investigated. Other methods to adjust the pH and keep the salt in solution need to be examined further before any toxicity tests can be performed. This was out of scope of the current thesis work.

Author evaluates the thesis results and conclusions as logical and in line with the set hypothesis. No major deviations or unexpected findings were observed during current work.

KOKKUVÖTE

Käesoleva lõputöö põhiprobleemiks oli uudsete fosforit sorbeerivate nanokomposiitmaterjalide keskkonnaohutuse hindamiseks vajalike andmete puudumine. Põhieesmärk sai lahendatud komposiitide, nende filtraatide ning lähtesoolade ökotoksikoloogilise toime määramisega kasutades testbaktereid *Vibrio fischeri*. Saadud tulemused on kokku võetud allpool ja neid käsitletakse üksikasjalikumalt käesoleva töö kolmandas peatükis.

Töö põhieesmärk jagati kolmeks alameesmärgiks: füüsikalise-keemiliste omaduste määramine, ökotoksikoloogilise toime esmane hindamine ning võimalike kandidaatide tuvastamine fosfori ärastamiseks kümne uuritud sorbeeriva nanokomposiitmaterjali hulgast. Alameesmärkidest saadud tulemuste põhjal tehti järgnevad järeldused:

1. Kuigi fosforit sorbeerivate komposiitmaterjalide primaarsuurus oli nanomõõtmetes, jäi uuritud materjalide keskmine hüdrodünaamiline diameeter pigem kõrgemasse nano- ning madalamasse mikrovahemikku: 186 (ZnFeZr 18:5:1) kuni 9406 (CaFe 2:1) nm.
2. *V. fischeri* kineetilise bioluminestsentsi inhibeerimise testi saab edukalt kasutada nanokomposiitmaterjalide ökotoksikoloogilise toime esmaseks hindamiseks.
3. Vastavalt saadud testandmetele (30 min EC₅₀ ja 24 h MBC väärtustele, mg / L) osutusid seitse (ZnFeZr 6:1:1, ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1, CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1, MgZnFe 1:1:1, CaFeZr 6:1:1, MgFeZr 6:1:1 ja CaFe 2:1) nanokomposiitmaterjali kümnest bakteritele *Vibrio fischeri* mitte mürgisteks (st 30 min EC₅₀ ja 24 h MBC väärtused > 100 mg / L).
4. Kaks nanokomposiitmaterjali, ZnFeZr 18:5:1 ja ZnFeZr 10:1:1, klassifitseerusid kahjulikuks (EC₅₀ > 10 - 100 mg / L), 30 minuti EC₅₀ väärtus vastavalt 36,86 ja 53,91 mg / L.
5. Tsingipõhiste nanokomposiitide toksikoloogiline toime sõltus peamiselt lahustunud tsingiioonidest suspensioonis – selles osas tuleb teha täiendavaid uuringuid.
6. Käesoleva uuringu tulemuste põhjal osutus ökotoksikoloogilise toime esmase hindamise ja fosfori adsorptsiooni efektiivsuse seisukohalt kõige sobivamaks nanokomposiitmaterjaliks ZnFeZr 6:1:1 (30 min EC₅₀ = 118,0 mg / L ja 24 h MBC = 250 mg / L).

Autor soovib täiendavalt uurida seitsme tsingipõhise nanokomposiitmaterjali võimalikku keskkonnaohtlikkust veeorganismidele, kasutades veekeskkonna erinevate troofiliste tasemete mudelorganisme (nt vetikad ja koorikloomad). Lisaks tuleks täiendavalt uurida mõnede lähtesoolade (nt Zr ja Fe) ohtlikkust. Enne toksilisuse katsete tegemist tuleb täiendavalt uurida meetodeid pH reguleerimiseks ja soola

lahuses hoidmiseks. Antud täiendavad uuringud on väljaspool käesoleva lõputöö käsitusala.

Autor hindab lõputöö tulemusi ja järeldusi loogilisteks ning püstitatud hüpoteesidele vastavateks. Antud töö käigus suuri kõrvalekaldeid eeldatud tulemustest ega ootamatuid leide ei täheldatud.

LIST OF REFERENCES

- [1] A. I. Drenkova-Tuhtan, ‘Nanocomposite Engineered Particles for Phosphorus Recovery and Toxicological Risk Assessment for the Aquatic Environment’. Jun. 03, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/867457>
- [2] V. Aruoja, S. Pokhrel, M. Sihtmaa, M. Mortimer, L. Maedler, and A. Kahru, ‘Toxicity of 12 metal-based nanoparticles to algae, bacteria and protozoa’, *Environ. Sci.-Nano*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 630–644, 2015, doi: 10.1039/c5en00057b.
- [3] A. Drenkova-Tuhtan *et al.*, ‘Pilot-scale removal and recovery of dissolved phosphate from secondary wastewater effluents with reusable ZnFeZr adsorbent @ Fe₃O₄/SiO₂ particles with magnetic harvesting’, *Water Res.*, vol. 109, pp. 77–87, Feb. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2016.11.039.
- [4] M. Schneider *et al.*, ‘Nanostructured ZnFeZr oxyhydroxide precipitate as efficient phosphate adsorber in waste water: understanding the role of different material-building-blocks’, *Environ. Sci.-Nano*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 180–190, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1039/c6en00507a.
- [5] A. Drenkova-Tuhtan *et al.*, ‘Influence of cation building blocks of metal hydroxide precipitates on their adsorption and desorption capacity for phosphate in wastewater—A screening study’, *Colloids Surf. Physicochem. Eng. Asp.*, vol. 488, pp. 145–153, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.colsurfa.2015.10.017.
- [6] H. Ohtake and S. Tsuneda, *Phosphorus Recovery and Recycling*. Singapore, SINGAPORE: Springer Singapore Pte. Limited, 2018. Accessed: Apr. 22, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/tuee/detail.action?docID=5402145>
- [7] D. Cordell and S. White, ‘Tracking phosphorus security: indicators of phosphorus vulnerability in the global food system’, *Food Secur.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 337–350, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s12571-015-0442-0.
- [8] ‘Countries With the Largest Phosphate Reserves’, *WorldAtlas*, Mar. 23, 2018. <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/countries-with-the-largest-phosphate-reserves.html> (accessed May 11, 2022).
- [9] ‘Critical raw materials’. https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/raw-materials/areas-specific-interest/critical-raw-materials_en (accessed Apr. 22, 2022).
- [10] ‘Recycled quota crucial for critical raw materials like phosphorous’. <https://www.easymining.se/newsroom/articles-news/quota/> (accessed Apr. 22, 2022).
- [11] W. K. Dodds *et al.*, ‘Eutrophication of U.S. Freshwaters: Analysis of Potential Economic Damages’, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 12–19, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.1021/es801217q.
- [12] P. Cornel and C. Schaum, ‘Phosphorus recovery from wastewater: needs, technologies and costs’, *Water Sci. Technol. J. Int. Assoc. Water Pollut. Res.*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 1069–1076, 2009, doi: 10.2166/wst.2009.045.
- [13] K. Ooi, A. Sonoda, Y. Makita, and M. Torimura, ‘Comparative study on phosphate adsorption by inorganic and organic adsorbents from a diluted solution’, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 3181–3189, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.jece.2017.06.015.
- [14] ‘Definition - Nanomaterials - Environment - European Commission’. https://ec.europa.eu/environment/chemicals/nanotech/faq/definition_en.htm (accessed May 13, 2022).
- [15] ‘Glossary: Nanomaterial’. https://ec.europa.eu/health/scientific_committees/opinions_layman/glossary/mno/nanomaterial.htm (accessed May 13, 2022).

- [16] ‘Glossary: Nanoscale’.
https://ec.europa.eu/health/scientific_committees/opinions_layman/glossary/mno/nanoscale.htm (accessed May 13, 2022).
- [17] Y. Xia, K. Dong, X. Xiang, W. Li, Y. Gong, and Z. Li, ‘Phosphorus hyperaccumulation in nano-MgO using a circular recovery process based on multiple phase transitions from periclase to brucite’, *Sci. Total Environ.*, vol. 727, p. 138510, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138510.
- [18] Y. Zhang, W. Zhang, and B. Pan, ‘Struvite-based phosphorus recovery from the concentrated bioeffluent by using HFO nanocomposite adsorption: Effect of solution chemistry’, *Chemosphere*, vol. 141, pp. 227–234, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2015.07.023.
- [19] N. Kamali, A. R. Mehrabadi, M. Mirabi, and M. A. Zahed, ‘Synthesis of vinasse-dolomite nanocomposite biochar via a novel developed functionalization method to recover phosphate as a potential fertilizer substitute’, *Front. Environ. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 14, no. 4, p. 70, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11783-020-1249-6.
- [20] Y. Zhang, Q. Tang, Y. Sun, C. Yao, Z. Yang, and W. Yang, ‘Improved utilization of active sites for phosphorus adsorption in FeOOH/anion exchanger nanocomposites via a glycol-solvothermal synthesis strategy’, *J. Environ. Sci.*, vol. 111, pp. 313–323, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jes.2021.04.018.
- [21] A. Kahru and A. Ivask, ‘Mapping the Dawn of Nanoecotoxicological Research’, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 823–833, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1021/ar3000212.
- [22] B. J. Dutka and G. Bitton, Eds., *Toxicity Testing Using Microorganisms*. New York: CRC Press, 2019. doi: 10.1201/9780429286810.
- [23] K. L. E. Kaiser and J. Devillers, *Handbooks of ecotoxicological data, Volume 2. Ecotoxicity of chemicals to Photobacterium phosphoreum*. Amsterdam: Gordon and Breach Science Publishers, 1994.
- [24] H. Urbanczyk, J. C. Ast, M. J. Higgins, J. Carson, and P. V. Dunlap, ‘Reclassification of *Vibrio fischeri*, *Vibrio logei*, *Vibrio salmonicida* and *Vibrio wodanis* as *Aliivibrio fischeri* gen. nov., comb. nov., *Aliivibrio logei* comb. nov., *Aliivibrio salmonicida* comb. nov. and *Aliivibrio wodanis* comb. nov.’, *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.*, vol. 57, no. Pt 12, pp. 2823–2829, Dec. 2007, doi: 10.1099/ijs.0.65081-0.
- [25] K. Gruiz, T. Meggyes, and E. Fenyvesi, *Engineering Tools for Environmental Risk Management: 2. Environmental Toxicology*. London, UNITED KINGDOM: Taylor & Francis Group, 2015. Accessed: Apr. 22, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://ebookcentral.proquest.com/lib/tuee/detail.action?docID=1591695>
- [26] D. J. Rodgerson, *Bioluminescence: Characteristics, Adaptations and Biotechnology (Biochemistry Research Trends)*. UK: Nova Science Publishers, Inc., 2011.
- [27] A. Bulich and D. Isenberg, ‘Use of the Luminescent Bacterial System for the Rapid Assessment of Aquatic Toxicity’, *Isa Trans.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 29–33, 1981.
- [28] K. L. E. Kaiser, ‘Correlations of *Vibrio fischeri* Bacteria Test Data with Bioassay Data for Other Organisms’, *Environ. Health Perspect.*, vol. 106, pp. 583–591, 1998, doi: 10.2307/3433809.
- [29] A. Kahru, ‘Ecotoxicological tests in non-ecotoxicological research: contribution to 3Rs. Use of luminescent photobacteria for evaluating the toxicity of 47 MEIC reference chemicals.’, *ALTEX* 3, pp. 302–308, 2006.
- [30] M. T. D. Cronin and T. W. Schultz, ‘Validation of *Vibrio fischeri* acute toxicity data: mechanism of action-based QSARs for non-polar narcotics and polar narcotic phenols’, *Sci. Total Environ.*, vol. 204, no. 1, pp. 75–88, Sep. 1997, doi: 10.1016/S0048-9697(97)00179-4.

- [31] A. M. Davis, '3.15 - Quantitative Structure–Activity Relationships', in *Comprehensive Medicinal Chemistry III*, S. Chackalamannil, D. Rotella, and S. E. Ward, Eds. Oxford: Elsevier, 2017, pp. 379–392. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-409547-2.12348-0.
- [32] O. Shimomura, *Bioluminescence: Chemical Principles and Methods*, Revised ed. edition. Singapore ; Hackensack, NJ: World Scientific Publishing Company, 2012.
- [33] ISO, 2010. *ISO 21338:2010: Water Quality—Kinetic Determination of the Inhibitory Effects of Sediment, Other Solids and Coloured Samples on the Light Emission of *Vibrio fischeri* (Kinetic Luminescent Bacteria Test)*. Geneva, Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization (ISO), 2010.
- [34] 'EVS-EN ISO 11348-3:2008/A1:2018', *EVS*. <https://www.evs.ee/et/evs-en-iso-11348-3-2008-a1-2018> (accessed Jul. 10, 2022).
- [35] J. Lappalainen, R. Juvonen, K. Vaajasaari, and M. Karp, 'A new flash method for measuring the toxicity of solid and colored samples', *Chemosphere*, vol. 38, no. 5, pp. 1069–1083, Feb. 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0045-6535(98)00352-X.
- [36] K. Mandel, A. Drenkova-Tuhtan, F. Hutter, C. Gellermann, H. Steinmetz, and G. Sextl, 'Layered double hydroxide ion exchangers on superparamagnetic microparticles for recovery of phosphate from waste water', *J. Mater. Chem. A*, vol. 1, no. 5, pp. 1840–1848, 2013, doi: 10.1039/c2ta00571a.
- [37] M. K. Tiwari, B. Gowrishankar, V. K. Raghuvanshi, R. V. Nandedkar, and K. J. S. Sawhney, 'Development of a total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometer for ultra-trace element analysis', *Bull. Mater. Sci.*, vol. 25, no. 5, pp. 435–441, Oct. 2002, doi: 10.1007/BF02708023.
- [38] S. C. Singh, H. B. Zeng, Chunlei Guo, and Weiping Cai, *Nanomaterials : Processing and Characterization with Lasers*.
- [39] T. Mudalige, H. Qu, D. Van Haute, S. M. Ansar, A. Paredes, and T. Ingle, 'Chapter 11 - Characterization of Nanomaterials: Tools and Challenges', in *Nanomaterials for Food Applications*, A. López Rubio, M. J. Fabra Rovira, M. Martínez Sanz, and L. G. Gómez-Mascaraque, Eds. Elsevier, 2019, pp. 313–353. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-814130-4.00011-7.
- [40] E. Vindimian, 'REGTOX Macro Excel'. 2018. Accessed: Jul. 20, 2022. [Online]. Available: http://www.normalesup.org/~vindimian/en_index.html
- [41] S. Suppi *et al.*, 'A novel method for comparison of biocidal properties of nanomaterials to bacteria, yeasts and algae', *J. Hazard. Mater.*, vol. 286, pp. 75–84, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.jhazmat.2014.12.027.
- [42] European Commission, *Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH), establishing a European Chemicals Agency, amending Directive 1999/45/EC and repealing Council Regulation (EEC) No 793/93 and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1488/94 as well as Council Directive 76/769/EEC and Commission Directives 91/155/EEC, 93/67/EEC, 93/105/EC and 2000/21/EC*, vol. 396. 2006. Accessed: Jul. 20, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2006/1907/oj/eng>
- [43] European Commission, *Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures, amending and repealing Directives 67/548/EEC and 1999/45/EC, and amending Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 (Text with EEA relevance)*, vol. 353. 2008. Accessed: Jul. 20, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2008/1272/oj/eng>

- [44] O. M. Bondarenko *et al.*, ‘Multilaboratory evaluation of 15 bioassays for (eco)toxicity screening and hazard ranking of engineered nanomaterials: FP7 project NANOVALID’, *Nanotoxicology*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp. 1229–1242, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1080/17435390.2016.1196251.
- [45] A. Käkinen, O. Bondarenko, A. Ivask, and A. Kahru, ‘The Effect of Composition of Different Ecotoxicological Test Media on Free and Bioavailable Copper from CuSO₄ and CuO Nanoparticles: Comparative Evidence from a Cu-Selective Electrode and a Cu-Biosensor’, *Sensors*, vol. 11, no. 11, Art. no. 11, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.3390/s111110502.
- [46] O. Bondarenko, K. Juganson, A. Ivask, K. Kasemets, M. Mortimer, and A. Kahru, ‘Toxicity of Ag, CuO and ZnO nanoparticles to selected environmentally relevant test organisms and mammalian cells in vitro: a critical review’, *Arch. Toxicol.*, vol. 87, no. 7, pp. 1181–1200, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s00204-013-1079-4.
- [47] M. Heinlaan, A. Ivask, I. Blinova, H.-C. Dubourguier, and A. Kahru, ‘Toxicity of nanosized and bulk ZnO, CuO and TiO₂ to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* and crustaceans *Daphnia magna* and *Thamnocephalus platyurus*’, *Chemosphere*, vol. 71, no. 7, pp. 1308–1316, Apr. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2007.11.047.
- [48] M. Mortimer, K. Kasemets, M. Heinlaan, I. Kurvet, and A. Kahru, ‘High throughput kinetic *Vibrio fischeri* bioluminescence inhibition assay for study of toxic effects of nanoparticles’, *Toxicol. In Vitro*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 1412–1417, Aug. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.tiv.2008.02.011.
- [49] ‘Homepage - ECHA’. <https://echa.europa.eu> (accessed May 20, 2022).
- [50] I. Kurvet *et al.*, ‘Toxicity of Nine (Doped) Rare Earth Metal Oxides and Respective Individual Metals to Aquatic Microorganisms *Vibrio fischeri* and *Tetrahymena thermophila*’, *Materials*, vol. 10, no. 7, Art. no. 7, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.3390/ma10070754.
- [51] ‘Kemikaaliteave - ECHA’. <https://echa.europa.eu/et/information-on-chemicals> (accessed Aug. 03, 2022).
- [52] ‘Registration Dossier - ECHA’. <https://echa.europa.eu/et/registration-dossier/-/registered-dossier/15087/6/2/6> (accessed Jul. 24, 2022).

Appendix 1 *Vibrio fischeri* inhibition percentages with standard deviations for composites

Concentration [mg / L]	Positive control ZnSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	Composite ZnFeZr 18:5:1	Composite ZnFeZr 10:1:1	Composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1	Composite ZnFeZr 4:1:1	Composite ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	Composite CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1
0,78	12,12 ± 2,23	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	-	6,7 ± 1,31	6,47 ± 1,75	6,71 ± 1,45	4,06 ± 1,13	5,58 ± 0,78	6,28 ± 1,63
1,56	15,35 ± 2,75	-	-	-	-	-	-
3,13	22,02 ± 2,14	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	-	6,5 ± 0,35	4,33 ± 0,68	-	-	-	-
6,25	39,86 ± 3,42	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	-	28,04 ± 13,12	20,11 ± 16,85	10,34 ± 3,22	6,06 ± 1,76	9,57 ± 1,18	9,68 ± 1,2
12,5	64,1 ± 3,01	-	-	-	-	-	-
25	82,98 ± 3,86	51,07 ± 0,59	37,91 ± 0,39	-	5,84 ± 2,18	-	-
50	92,52 ± 2,88	59,59 ± 0,8	51,06 ± 0,23	34,51 ± 0,07	25,28 ± 3,68	-	-
100	96,75 ± 1,46	68,39 ± 15,66	62,99 ± 17,29	42,64 ± 8,98	46,82 ± 9,19	37,26 ± 5,75	44,69 ± 7,66
250	-	78,59 ± 11,2	75,85 ± 13,99	66,69 ± 10,47	71,76 ± 8,08	57,74 ± 5,12	68,93 ± 5,48
500	-	85,3 ± 8,29	85,03 ± 10,26	80,79 ± 8,35	81,9 ± 6,87	71,88 ± 3,52	82,81 ± 3,58
1000	-	90,4 ± 6,44	91,18 ± 7,19	87,41 ± 1,79	89,36 ± 3,76	84,07 ± 2,2	91,67 ± 1,95
2000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Appendix 1 continued *Vibrio fischeri* inhibition percentages with standard deviations for composites

Concentration [mg / L]	Composite MgZnFe 1:1:1	Composite CaFeZr 6:1:1	Composite MgFeZr 6:1:1	Composite CaFe 2:1	Composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs
0,78	-	-	-	-	-
1	2,84 ± 1,79	2,15 ± 1,83	2,91 ± 1,02	1,65 ± 2,2	3,08 ± 1,85
1,56	-	-	-	-	-
3,13	-	-	-	-	-
5	-	-	-	-	-
6,25	-	-	-	-	-
10	3,09 ± 5,39	-1,07 ± 2,42	-0,02 ± 1	-1,17 ± 2,45	5,56 ± 1,32
12,5	-	-	-	-	-
25	-	-	-	-	-
50	-	-	-	-	-
100	16,22 ± 8,53	-17,78 ± 2,17	-12,64 ± 1,55	-35,22 ± 2,93	7,28 ± 1,19
250	31,85 ± 13,42	-24,33 ± 9,67	-5,15 ± 3,05	-80,18 ± 18,49	12,03 ± 3,5
500	48,1 ± 20,05	-28,29 ± 8,32	-0,26 ± 1,61	-113,09 ± 22,09	19,02 ± 13,5
1000	71,24 ± 21,2	-46,89 ± 7,25	-1,59 ± 2,29	-163,62 ± 20,16	41,36 ± 15,46
2000	-	-	-	-	74,86 ± 5,69
2500	-	-	-	-	87,09 ± 4,02

Appendix 2 *Vibrio fischeri* inhibition percentages with standard deviations for filtrates

Concentration [mg / L]	Filtrate ZnFeZr 18:5:1	Filtrate ZnFeZr 10:1:1	Filtrate ZnFeZr 6:1:1	Filtrate ZnFeZr 4:1:1	Filtrate ZnFeZr 3,6:0,2:1	Filtrate CaZnFeZr 3:3:1:1	Filtrate MgZnFe 1:1:1	Filtrate ZnFeZr 6:1:1 on MPs
1	2,33 ± 1,56	1,24 ± 1,02	3,93 ± 1,18	3,33 ± 0,94	2,44 ± 0,65	2,92 ± 1,18	2,17 ± 0,52	3,29 ± 0,78
10	2,98 ± 2,23	2,83 ± 1,26	5,58 ± 0,99	4,87 ± 0,69	3,29 ± 0,28	5,28 ± 0,81	2,28 ± 0,56	-
100	8,62 ± 1,56	7,24 ± 1,37	12,91 ± 1,12	11,84 ± 0,78	9,88 ± 0,3	14,45 ± 1,02	2,55 ± 0,64	4,61 ± 1,4
500	17,98 ± 2,02	13,41 ± 2,9	30,63 ± 2,27	24,66 ± 1,61	19,07 ± 0,81	46,44 ± 0,13	3,39 ± 0,3	11,02 ± 2,32
1000	30,72 ± 5,28	22,14 ± 7,14	56,38 ± 0,56	47,47 ± 2,88	35,29 ± 2,2	71,88 ± 2,24	4,63 ± 1,07	14,52 ± 4,22
2000	56,61 ± 7,76	48,89 ± 11,08	82,11 ± 2,45	75,29 ± 2,18	63,01 ± 3,42	88,7 ± 2,38	7,98 ± 1,53	19,09 ± 7,58
2500	65,2 ± 8,31	60,26 ± 10,72	88,13 ± 2,52	83,16 ± 1,3	71,26 ± 3,97	92,1 ± 2,16	8,27 ± 1,65	-
3000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	24,61 ± 10,24
4000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	31,51 ± 11,7
5000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	37,31 ± 12,32

Appendix 3 *Vibrio fischeri* inhibition percentages with standard deviations for precursor salts

Concentration [mg / L]	Precursor salt CaCl₂ · 2H₂O	Precursor salt MgCl₂ · 6H₂O	Precursor salt ZnCl₂	Precursor salt FeCl₃ · 6H₂O	Precursor salt ZrOCl₂ · 8H₂O
0,1	1,13 ± 1,71	2,42 ± 0,19	-	3,63 ± 1,08	1,3 ± 0,88
0,4	-	-	4,19 ± 0,53	-	-
0,8	-	-	6,68 ± 0,68	-	-
1	1,29 ± 2,18	1,75 ± 0,23	-	36,35 ± 2	6,12 ± 1,01
1,6	-	-	9,42 ± 0,97	-	-
2,5	-	-	-	97,69 ± 0,42	25,5 ± 2,02
3,1	-	-	11,74 ± 1,9	-	-
5	-	-	-	99,84 ± 0,05	91,21 ± 4,59
6,3	-	-	15,34 ± 1,78	-	-
10	-0,49 ± 1,48	1,12 ± 0,86	-	99,85 ± 0,04	99,82 ± 0,01
12,5	-	-	31,98 ± 1,63	-	-
25	-	-	67,05 ± 1,89	-	-
50	-	-	88,97 ± 0,28	-	-
100	-1,27 ± 2,07	-0,92 ± 1,04	-	99,85 ± 0,05	99,82 ± 0,01
500	-	-	-	-	-
1000	12,41 ± 6,13	13,6 ± 5,82	-	99,75 ± 0,01	99,78 ± 0,01